

BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

DEPARTMENT OF HORTICULTURE

**GROWTH AND YIELD PERFORMANCE OF HYBRID TOMATO (*Lycopersicon
esculentum* Mill) VARIETIES UNDER POLYHOUSE DURING RAINY SEASON AT
KOGA IRRIGATION SCHEME, NORTHWEST, ETHIOPIA**

M.Sc. Thesis

By

Zenebe Abebu

March 2024

Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

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**SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT FOR THE
MASTER OF SCIENCE DEGREE (M.SC.) IN HORTICULTURE**

March 2024

Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

THESIS APPROVAL SHEET

As member of the Board of Examiners of the Master of Sciences (M.Sc.) thesis open defense examination, we have read and evaluated this thesis prepared by Mr. Zenebe Abebu entitled **Growth and Yield Performance of Hybrid Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculuntem* Mill) Varieties under Polyhouse during Rainy Season at Koga Irrigation Scheme, Northwest, Ethiopia.** We hereby certify that the thesis is accepted for fulfilling the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of Sciences (M.Sc.) in Horticulture.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that this thesis entitled **Growth and Yield Performance of Hybrid Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculuntem* Mill) Varieties under Polyhouse during Rainy Season at Koga Irrigation Scheme, Northwest, Ethiopia**. Submitted to in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of M.Sc., in “**Horticulture**” to College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Bahir Dar University through the Department of Horticulture, done by **Mr. Zenebe Abebu**, Id.No. BDU1401193 is an authentic work carried out by him under our guidance. The matter embodied in this project work has not been submitted earlier for the award of any degree or diploma to the best of my knowledge and belief.

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my beloved families; they sacrificed everything to ensure my better future, wellbeing and welfare.

ABBREVIATION AND ACRONYMS

ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
ARC	Agriculture Research Center
CEC	Cation Exchange Capacity
CRD	Completely Randomized Design
CSA	Central Statistical Agency
EHDA	Ethiopian Horticulture Development Association
EIAR	Ethiopian Institution of Agricultural Research
ERCA	Ethiopian Revenues and Customs Authority
FAO	Food and Agricultural Organization
GI	Galvanized Iron
KHDP	Kerala Horticulture Development Programme
LSD	Least Significant Difference
MoA	Minister of Agriculture
MoANR	Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resource
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PLC	Private Limited Company
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
SAS	Statistical Analysis System
SNV	Stichting Nederlandse Vrijwilligers
ToANV	Tomato Apex Necrosis Virus
TYLCV	Tomato Yellow Leaf curl Virus
USA	United State America
USDA	United State Department of Agriculture
USDANRCS	United State Department of Agriculture Natural Resource Conservation

Growth and Yield Performance of Hybrid Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculuntem* Mill) Varieties under Polyhouse during Rainy Season at Koga Irrigation Scheme, Northwest, Ethiopia

By: Zenebe Abebu

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ABSTRACT

Tomato production in Ethiopia is mostly practiced during the off season using irrigation. During the rainy season, its production is limited due to high incidence of fungal diseases. The market supply of tomatoes during the rainy season is therefore limited and drives the prices to unaffordable high level. Recently, however, smallholder farmers are using Polyhouse technology that protects tomatoes from rain and thus reduces the incidence of diseases, especially that of late blight. Therefore, a field experiment was conducted at Koga Irrigation Scheme to evaluate the growth and yield performance of hybrid tomato varieties and economics of polyhouse structures during the rainy season. Accordingly, three hybrid tomato varieties (Galilea, Gabbi and Galilea-39) were grown under polyhouse during the 2022 rainy season in four replications at Koga Irrigation Scheme, which were arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Data on growth, phenology, yield and quality parameters of tomato were collected and analyzed using the SAS-9.4 software. According to the results significant differences among the three hybrid tomato varieties were observed for most of the growth parameters and yield components in each location. Gabbi variety recorded the tallest plant height (174.84-180.54 cm), more number of primary branches (8.91-9.72) and secondary branches (17.30-19.32), the highest number of flower cluster (29.75-34.45), flower per cluster (6.86-7.36), fruit per cluster (5.29-6.01), fruit set percentage (72.64-84.10%), marketable yield (90.75-103.07t/ha) and total yield (92.20-104.31 t/ha) in all locations except in Kudmi. Combined over locations Gabbi variety recorded the tallest plant height (174.63 cm), more number of primary branches (8.60) and secondary branches (17.61), the highest number of flower clusters per plant (29.17), number of flowers (6.68) and number of fruits per cluster (5.00), the longest fruit length (6.83cm), the highest marketable yield (89.11 t/ha) and total fruit yield (90.32 t/ha). Financial feasibility of the polyhouse also showed that net present value of producing tomatoes in the polyhouse with 18% discount rate was non-negative (4,135.27ETB per 140m² area); the benefit to cost ratio was 1.25 and the internal rate of return was 24% at 18% interest rate. Accordingly, the production of tomato in a polyhouse structure is highly feasible and profitable where the variety Gabbi could be recommended for the production of tomato at Koga Irrigation Scheme and similar agro-ecology. Further researches on fertilizer optimization and disease and insect pest management options are suggested.

Key Words: Financial feasibility, Gabbi variety, Fruit set percentage

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Chapter 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and Justification

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) belongs to the family *Solanaceae* and it is one of the economically important vegetable crops grown worldwide under outdoor and indoor conditions (MoA, 2013; Damtew Abewoy, 2017). The family also includes other well-known species such as potato, tobacco, peppers and eggplant.

Tomatoes have high yielding potential and are important source of income for small farmers and provide employment opportunities in the production, distribution and processing industries (Lemma Dessalegn, 2002). The crop is one of the strategic commodities supported by the Ethiopian Government prioritized for agro-industry development (Brasceso *et al.*, 2019). It plays an important role in Ethiopia's poverty and food insecurity reduction programs because of its short harvest season and relatively high productivity (Dagmawe Menelek, 2021).

Tomato is a good source of micronutrients, fiber, vitamins, minerals and organic acids that can be used in many forms such as raw vegetables in sandwiches and processed products like syrup, ketchup, juice paste, etc. (NARC, 2013; Maharjan, 2019). It is known as the poor man's orange and is said to be a good remedy for constipated sufferers (Parajuli, 2015). Tomato has high content in lycopene (Trinklein, 2010), the pigment that makes tomatoes red and has been linked to preventing or fighting many types of cancer, especially prostate cancer (Giovannucci, 1999).

According to FAO (2022), the world tomato production in 2021 was 189.1 million tons produced on 5,167,087 ha of land with the productivity of 36.6 t/ha. China accounts 35% of the world total production followed by India, the European Union, Turkey and the United States. In Ethiopia, the total production of about 42,181.61 tons, which were harvested from 6,754 hectares of land, with a productivity of about 6.25 t/ha during the 2021 production season (FAO, 2021). The overall production and productivity of tomato in Ethiopia is very

low compared to other countries due to various challenges such as unsuitable environmental conditions, pest and disease infestations, and limited access to improved technologies (Tewdros Tesfaye *et al.*, 2016).

Tomatoes are commonly grown in tropical, subtropical, and temperate climates. For optimal growth and development, the plant needs warm weather and plenty of sunshine. Tomatoes need a temperature between 21 and 27 °C for optimal growth and development (Hanson, 2001; Shankara *et al.*, 2005). If tomatoes are exposed to temperatures of 12°C or lower, cold damages can be occurred. In addition, tomatoes need an even supply of moisture and well-drained soil. Therefore, in temperate and subtropical climates where environmental conditions are unsuitable, especially during the winter season, tomatoes are grown under sheltered structures, while in tropical countries they are mostly grown under open field conditions (Kelley *et al.*, 2014).

In Ethiopia, tomatoes are grown in open field during the off season using irrigation. The production of tomatoes during the rainy season is limited, which is associated with high humidity that increases the incidence of diseases especially that of late blight (*Phytophthora infestation* (Mont de Bary) as indicated by Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu (2017). Heavy rainfall, high temperatures, and high relative humidity are the typical features of subtropical or tropical climates that increase the incidences of late blight (Xie *et al.*, 2015; Hagassou, 2019), fruit cracking (Peet, 2012), and affect the fruit quality and quantity. This situation reduces the market supply of tomatoes during the rainy season, which in turn causes price escalation, which is not affordable by the consumers.

Currently polyhouse/rain-shelter technology is developed and promoted in various countries including Africa as alternative production system for tomatoes and similar vegetable during rainy season in humid and sub-humid climates. This technology reduces the predisposition of tomato plants against late blight and other similar diseases as indicated by various researches (Palada *et al.*, 2003; Kratky, 2006; Srinivasan, 2011; Wani *et al.*, 2011). These plastic houses not only protect the crop from rain, but also keep the insect pests away, allowing for profitable tomato cultivation during the hot and wet season.

Polyhouse is an innovative solution that can help farmers protect their crops from harsh weather conditions, increase yields, and improve their income (Kratky, 2006). It has been introduced in Malaysia for commercial production of selected high-value crops such as tomato (Singh, 2011). Polyhouse technology used in increasing the yield of red chili and reduce the risk of crop failure due to extreme weather conditions in Indonesia province of Aceh Tengah (Fajri *et al.*, 2023). The technology is being implemented in different parts of Africa, including Ethiopia, and has the potential to improve vegetable production for smallholders as indicated by various researchers (Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu, 2017; Nordey *et al.*, 2017; Dessie Getahun, 2019; Misganaw Anteneh *et al.*, 2021). Polyhouse/rain shelter is practiced in Ethiopia to produce fresh tomatoes with high quality and yield in the rainy period. A study conducted in Fogera plain, North Western Ethiopia, found that plastic shelter tomato production method under rain-fed conditions was economically feasible and increased tomato yield (Misganaw Anteneh *et al.*, 2021).

Tomato cultivation in the plastic house is comparatively free from pest and disease infestation. The fruit yield of tomatoes in plastic house conditions increased compared to outdoor conditions due to the minimal presence of pests and insects under a plastic house (Pramila and Aarya, 2019). Some farmers practice growing tomatoes outdoors with heavy use of fungicides to control late blight despite low yields (CADP, 2008). This practice has increased over the spraying of fungicides, which are environmentally unfriendly and poses serious human health risks. The use of rain shelters can help minimize or avoid the use of fungicides by reducing the amount of rainfall that comes into contact with the plants, and thus reducing the amount of fungicide residue that is washed off (Børve and Stensvand, 2003; Brun *et al.*, 2023).

It is well-known that an appropriate variety under proper management gives high yield. But varietal studies conducted so far in tomato crop has revealed that the variety suitable for open field condition may not be suitable for plastic house. Most of the tomato varieties set fruit poorly even under plastic house conditions (Budhathoki *et al.*, 2004). In Ethiopia, Melkasalsa and Melkashola varieties are produced in low cost plastic rain shelter as indicated by (Dessie Getahun, 2019; Misganaw Anteneh *et al.*, 2021).

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Tomatoes are an important source of income for small farmers and commercial farmers in Ethiopia. They are mostly grown in open field during the offseason using irrigation. However, tomato production in the open field during the rainy season was difficult, mainly due to high rainfall and disease infestation that led to the complete destruction of the plants (Dessie Getahun, 2019). Tomatoes are abundantly available during the irrigation season, leads to a market surplus, resulting a drastically reduced prices. During the rainy season, adverse weather conditions like excessive rainfall or flooding can disrupt tomato cultivation, causing a decrease in supply and resulting in price increases (Dessie Getahun, 2019; Misganaw Anteneh *et al.*, 2021). Tomato is not a crop of choice by the farmers for rainy season production due to susceptibility to diseases and pest in North *Mecha woreda* associated with high rainfall (Kassa Getu, 2018). However, in North *Mecha* and *Dera woreda* some farmers practiced producing tomato during rainy season, using polyhouse technology. The technology provides protection against adverse weather conditions; reduce the risk of diseases and pest infestations.

Farmers in North *Mecha Woreda* produce different tomato varieties randomly during the rainy season using polyhouse technology. However, there is no availability of information towards suitable tomato varieties for rainy season production under polyhouse technology and there is no information about the profitability of producing tomatoes in the polyhouse technology. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the responses of tomato varieties to polyhouse production system, with the aim of ultimately identifying suitable varieties for polyhouse technology in the study area and the profitability of the polyhouse technology.

1.3. Objectives of the study

1.3.1. General objective of the study

To contribute for improvement of production and productivity of tomatoes in the study area.

1.3.2. Specific objective of the study

- To identify the best performed tomato variety/ies in the polyhouse in the study area.
- To evaluate the economical profitability of polyhouse for production of tomatoes.

1.4. Definition of terms

Payback Period (PBP): also called pay-off period is defined as the period required recovering the original investment outlay through the accumulated net cash flows earned by the project.

Internal Rate of Return (IRR): is an indicator of the efficiency or quality of an investment. A project is a good investment position if its IRR is greater than the interest rate that could be earned by alternate investments or putting the money in a bank account.

Net present value (NPV): is defined as the total present (discounted) value of a time series of cash flows. It is an indicator of how much value an investment or project adds to the capital invested. In principle a project is accepted if the NPV is non-negative.

Benefit to cost ratio (BCR): is defined as the sum discounted benefit divided by discounted cost. When $BCR > 1$, accept the project, When $BCR < 1$, reject the project, When $BCR = 1$, be indifferent.

Chapter 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Origin and Distribution of Tomatoes

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill), is believed to have originated from Andean regions which is now part of Bolivia, Colombia, Chile and Peru. Although the history of early original locations of tomato domestication has been reported unclearly, there are two hypotheses that have been developed for the actual origin of tomato. The first hypothesis suggests Peru while the second hypothesis suggests Mexico as the places of origin of tomato domestication (Peralta and Spooner, 2007). Although domestication is still unclear, linguistic evidence however suggests that Peru and Mexico are the main domestication regions (Peralta *et al.*, 2006). It is known that tomatoes were grown in Mexico as early as 500 BC used for cooking by the Aztecs and brought to the rest of the world by the conquistadors after conquering Aztec territory (Bergougnoux, 2014).

Tomato was introduced to Europe after the Spanish colonization of the Americas, and cultivation began in the 15th and 16th century (Smith, 2001) and later spread to South and East Asia, Africa and the Middle East (Richard, 2014). Tomatoes were first introduced to the sub-region of West Africa by the Portuguese between the 16th and 17th centuries and became one of the most widely accepted vegetables (Norman, 1992; Osei *et al.*, 2010). In Ethiopia, there is no precise information on when the tomato was first introduced. However, the plant is cultivated in several main growing areas of the country (Lema Desalegn *et al.*, 2003; Getachew Etana and Tewdros Mulualem, 2019).

2.2. Botany of Tomato Plants

Tomato is a flowering plant in the nightshade family (*Solanaceae*) that is widely cultivated for its edible fruit (Padmini, 2006; Amsalu Ayana *et al.*, 2014). It is diploid and has a chromosome number of $2n = 2x = 24$ (Wu and Tanksley, 2010). From a botanical point of view, the tomato is considered a fruit because it develops from an ovary. However, it is often

consumed as a vegetable in cooking. Under optimal conditions, tomatoes have a life cycle of 95 to 115 days depending on the variety (McKenzie, 2014).

Tomatoes are a perennial herb but are often grown as an annual crop, although biennial forms exist. It is mostly a self-pollinating (autogamous) crop. However, it can also be a cross-pollinated perennial of the nightshade family, having a weak stem that often spreads along the ground (Agong *et al.*, 2001; Shankara *et al.*, 2005).

Based on the growth habits, tomatoes can be categorized in two types. The growth habit of tomato plants varies from indeterminate to determinate. Determinate tomatoes have a bush like habit, often expressed as bush tomatoes have a defined period of flowering and fruit development causing the vine to quit growing at a certain height (Dessie Getahun and Birhanu Habte, 2015). The plant requires minimal staking. Determinate tomatoes can be grown both in greenhouses and open fields. But, these tomatoes are usually grown in open fields and are intended for fresh consumption (Cheng *et al.*, 2016).

Indeterminate tomato varieties are vining plants that continue to grow longer and set fruit throughout the growing season and will require staking in order to support the plant (Dessie Getahun and Birhanu Habte, 2015). They will also require pruning in order to maximize fruit production; otherwise they continue growing new branches at the expense of producing fruit (Lunt, 2013). Indeterminate tomato cultivars have been largely produced by plant breeders for the protected cropping industry where there is a high capital investment per unit area. They are mostly grown vertically on a trellis system in a Greenhouse to maximize space (Mngoma, 2020). Indeterminate tomato varieties are also used in some open field production systems where high quality fresh fruits are required, usually for salad or 'slicing' (George, 2009).

The stem of tomato plant is angular and covered with hairy and glandular trichomes that give a distinctive smell. It has a weak stem (vines) which require staking during its production, especially in the indeterminate species (Lemma Desalegn *et al.*, 2003).

Tomato plants are generally branched, spreading horizontally up to 60-180 cm. However, some cultivars are compact (determined) (Naika *et al.*, 2005). The tomato plants have compound leaves, which are made up of leaflets and are distributed along the leaf axils. The leaves are more or less hairy, strongly scented, and pinnate and up to 45 cm long. While the entire leaf is connected to the stem by the petiole, the leaflets are connected to the leaf axil by the petiole. The shape of the leaves ranges from lobed to compound, with the segments pinnate. Compound leaves typically consist of five to nine leaflets. The leaflets are petiolated and dentated. All leaves are covered with glandular, hairy trichomes (OECD, 2017).

Tomato fruits vary in width from 1.5 to 7.5 cm. The fruits are usually red, scarlet, or yellow, although green and purple cultivars also exist, and their shape varies from nearly spherical to oval and oblong to pear-shaped. Its fruit also contains at least two cells of small seeds surrounded by jelly-like pulp (Naika *et al.*, 2005). Botanically, the fruit shares all of the common characteristics of berries; a simple fleshy fruit that encloses its seed in the pulp. The outer membrane is a thin and fleshy tissue that covers the rest of the pericarp as well as the placenta. Between 50 and 200 seeds are located in the locular cavities and are surrounded by gelatinous membranes. The seed contains the embryo and endosperm and is covered by a strong seed coat called the testa (OECD, 2008).

2.3. Ecological Requirement of Tomato

Tomatoes are known as a warm season crop. It is grown in a wide range of climatic conditions from temperate to hot and humid tropical climates. It requires warm, clear and dry conditions. It grows in altitudes between 700 and 2000 meters above sea level (Lemma Dessalegn, 2002). The optimal temperatures for most tomato varieties are between 20 and 27 °C. Tomato plants can survive certain higher or lower temperature ranges, but plant tissue is damaged below 10 °C and above 38 °C (Naika *et al.*, 2005). The minimum night time temperature is important as a temperature below 21°C can cause fruit breakage and above 35°C can dry out the surface of both the pollen grain and stigma resulting in poor fruit set. Pollen germination rate increases with temperatures up to a certain point, but above 37°C germination is severely inhibited. Temperatures above 40°C can damage both ovules and

pollen production (Nicola *et al.*, 2009). High temperatures also slowdown the synthesis of the red pigment (lycopene) while the orange pigment, β -carotene, may continue to accumulate normally (Naika *et al.*, 2005).

For the optimal development of the tomato plant, a relative humidity between 65% and 85% is required. Higher relative humidity levels negatively influence pollen release and distribution on the stigma (Tormo Molina *et al.*, 2001). High humidity also creates a favorable environment for the development of various foliar diseases (Peet, 2008). The incidence of blotchy ripening also increases at high humidity. Conversely, low relative humidity may cause infertility, due to pollen drying before germination of the pollen on the stigma, which leads to small, deformed or hollow fruit (Starke Ayres, 2021). The crop is grown with annual rainfall ranging from 700 to over 1400 mm in different seasons under different weather conditions at different levels of technology and yield (Birhanu Kibebew and Tilhun Ketema, 2010).

Tomatoes grow well on most mineral soils, but they prefer deep, well-drained sandy loams. Deep tillage enables adequate root penetration in heavy clay-type soils, thus allowing the production of tomato. Sandy soils are preferable when an early harvest is desired. The favorable pH value is between 5.5 and 7.0. At higher or lower pH values phosphorus and certain micronutrients (Fe) become less available for plant uptake (Lemma Dessalegn, 2002).

2.4. Importance of Tomato Crops

2.4.1. Nutritional values and health benefits of tomato

Tomato fruits are widely used in human nutrition, both as fresh, ripe fruits and in the form of various products (Takac *et al.*, 2007). Tomatoes are considered a protective food because they contain nutrients such as beta-carotene, lycopene, vitamin C, and vitamin A (Fentik, 2017). It is also rich in minerals, sugars, essential amino acids, iron, fiber and phosphorus (Bhowmik *et al.*, 2012).

Tomatoes are a good source of lycopene, which is known to prevent the harmful effects of free radicals and various types of cancer and cardiovascular disease (Pila *et al.*, 2010). Consumption of 100 g of fresh tomatoes covers over 46%, 8% and 3.4% of the daily requirement of vitamin A (900 UE), vitamin C (82.5 mg) and potassium (3500 mg) respectively (Gebhardt and Thomas, 2002; Canene *et al.*, 2005). In addition, processed tomatoes such as soup, paste, concentrate; juice and ketchup also contribute positively to human health due to the content of said compounds in these products (Bergougnoux, 2014). The vitamin A contained in tomatoes improves vision and prevents the development of night blindness (Ganesan *et al.*, 2012).

2.4.2. Economic and social value of tomato

Tomatoes are one of the most economically important vegetable crops grown in many parts of the world, contributing significantly to the income security and nutritious diet of many households. In terms of global vegetable production, tomato ranks third next to potatoes and sweet potatoes, but ranks first as a processing crop (Melese Worku and Samul Sahela, 2018). It is used in various raw and processing materials. Fresh tomatoes are important ingredients around the world and processed tomatoes are used to make soups, juices and other products.

Tomato is one of the most important and well-known vegetable crops in Ethiopia. Tomato cultivation in rural communities is one of the major sources of income of the smallholder farmers (Naika *et al.*, 2005). Exporting tomato plant products to different countries plays an important role in a country's economic growth. It also strengthens the national economy as a source of raw materials for value-added agro-processing industries and as a source of foreign exchange for exportable tomatoes to international markets (Haji, 2008; Kanna, 2016).

The export earnings of tomatoes in the world have been increasing in recent years. In 2020 Mexico was the largest exporter of tomatoes, with 1,826,715 tons and a value of 2.6 billion dollar, accounting for 23.5% of the total volume and 26.4% of the total value of world exports (FAOSTAT, 2020). The Netherlands and Spain followed with 1,024,069 and 734,223 tons, respectively (Angel, 2022). According to the report by Observatory of Economic Complexity,

between 2020 and 2021, the exports of fresh or chilled tomatoes grew by 5.23%, from 9.82 billion dollar to 10.3 billion dollar. Mexico was the top exporter of fresh or chilled tomatoes in 2021, with a value of 2.57 billion dollar. European countries sold the highest value for exported tomatoes during 2021 with shipments amounting to 4.7 billion dollar or 45.1% of worldwide exports (Workman, 2022).

Studies indicated that most of Ethiopia's fruits and vegetables are grown for local consumption. However, considerable amounts of fruits and vegetables grown on small private farms in Eastern Ethiopia are exported (Kassa Getu, 2018). The Ethiopian Fruit and Vegetables Marketing Enterprise (ETFRUIT) are involved in the export of vegetables, including tomatoes, primarily to neighboring countries such as Djibouti and Somalia, sourcing them from the Hararghe and Rift-valley regions (Bezabih Emanu *et al*, 2015). The export of fruit and vegetables from Ethiopia, including tomatoes, is growing, with increasing interest from Europe and the Middle East (Wiersinga and Jager, 2009). This indicates a potential market for Ethiopian tomato exports to these regions. In 2015, Ethiopia exported 29,877.45 tons tomatoes to seven countries like Sudan, Nigeria, Yemen, Saudi Arabia and other Middle East countries and earned 192,151,623 million ETB or 9,246,060 USD (ERCA, 2015). As indicated by Dagmawi Menelek (2021), Ethiopia earned 9.006 million dollar from both fresh and chilled tomato exports.

2.5. Potentials and Constraints of Tomato Production in Ethiopia

Ethiopia has diverse agro-ecological zones for tomato cultivation as well as plentiful water sources, cheap labor (skilled and unskilled) and market availability in the world and neighboring country (EHDA, 2013). During (2020) cropping calendar, tomato production in Ethiopia was about 46,324.8 tons which was harvested from 6,434 hectares where its average productivity is 7.2 t/ha (FAO, 2020). The overall productivity of tomatoes in Ethiopia is very low as compared with average yields of 122, 59.24, 48.1 and 40.7 t/ha in USA, Europe, Asia and the entire world, respectively (FAO, 2020).

This low production and productivity of tomatoes in Ethiopia is associated among other with lack of improved high-yielder cultivars and improper agronomic practices, high incidence of diseases and insect pests, depletion of soil fertility, poor infrastructure, high post harvest losses and poor marketing systems (Lemma Desalegn, 2002; Gabriel, 2021). According to Gemechis *et al.* (2012), the use of inappropriate technology and improper irrigation practices in tomato production can result in crop failure. Limited availability of pesticides, fungicides, and other inputs necessary for tomato production can impact the productivity of the crop (Kifle Degefa *et al.*, 2022).

Post-harvest loss in tomato production in Ethiopia poses significant constraints on the industry. These losses have detrimental effects on the incomes of smallholder farmers and traders (Bezabih Emanu *et al.*, 2017). According to Zelalem Sisay *et al.* (2021), the shortage of recommended information on best practices for tomato production, including post-harvest handling and storage techniques, contributes to higher post-harvest losses. Improper packaging and storage practices can result in physical damage, spoilage, and decay of tomatoes, leading to higher post-harvest losses (Khatun and Rahman, 2018). Inadequate knowledge and resources for disease and pest management can result in higher incidences of crop diseases and pest infestations, leading to increased post-harvest losses (Zelalem Sisay *et al.*, 2021).

Poor marketing systems in tomato production in Ethiopia can lead to various problems. Farmers may have difficulty accessing markets due to a lack of information about market opportunities or a lack of transportation options (Meniga, 2014; Beneyam Tadesse *et al.*, 2021; Ddamulira *et al.*, 2021). Without proper storage facilities, tomatoes can spoil quickly, leading to post-harvest losses and reduced market acceptability and profits for farmers (Abubakari, 2014; Meniga, 2014; Beneyam Tadesse *et al.*, 2021). To address these constraints, there is a need for improved marketing systems that can provide farmers with better access to markets information, and storage of facilities. This could include the development of new market-oriented tomato varieties, improved access to credit, and initiatives to reduce post-harvest losses (Abubakari, 2014; Ddamulira *et al.*, 2021).

According to Dessie Getahun (2019), the production of tomato in the open field during the rainy season is difficult, due to high disease infestation associated with high rainfall. Due to prolonged showers and high soil moisture during the rainy season, the yield and quality of tomato drastically reduces (Lopez-Marin *et al.*, 2019). In addition, production of tomatoes during the rainy season is limited by unfavorable conditions such as hail, flooding and strong winds. These conditions, causing flower and immature fruit drop and damage to the foliage which can significantly reduce tomato yields (Misganaw Anteneh *et al.*, 2021). The direct contact of plants to rain drops makes the micro environments around the tomato plants suitable for the development and spreading of fungal diseases as indicated by Phiri (2011). Consequently, farmers obtain low yields and poor quality tomato fruits which ultimately result in low income.

2.6. Introduction and Structures of Polyhouse

Polyhouse/rain shelter is a new technology introduced in Ethiopia for the commercial production of selected high-value crops such as tomatoes (Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu, 2017; Dessie Getahun, 2019; Misganaw Anteneh *et al.*, 2021). It generally consists of a structural frame covered with polyethylene film or rigid plastic sheets on top of the structure, and possibly a screen on the sides and ends (Kratky, 2006). They typically do not contain active heating or cooling equipment and do not have electricity, but an irrigation source is necessary (Latifah *et al.*, 2015). In addition, plastic materials such as PVC pipes and locally available materials such as bamboo and wood can be also used as framing materials (Kratky, 2006).

Unlike traditional or high-tech greenhouses, the Polyhouse does not have a special device for regulating the environmental parameters. Opening the side walls can lower the temperature in summer, and such a structure can be used as a polyhouse for crop cultivation (Pack and Mehta, 2012). The internal environment of a plastic shelter depends on the radiant heat that the structure receives. Excessive radiation leads to heat stress in plants and impairs physiological functions and this excess heat must be dissipated through proper ventilation (Sharif *et al.*, 2008). Environmental patterns can be used to determine the strategic steps to

take to control the effects of heat stress and to design more effective environmental control systems (Latifah *et al.*, 2015).

The polyhouses are designed to ensure good ventilation to avoid temperature rises inside the houses. High temperatures inside the houses lead to problems such as poor fruit formation or damaged fruit, especially puffy tomato fruit. Therefore, in addition to the well-ventilated structure of the houses attention must also be paid to cultural management to prevent crop damage caused by high temperatures (Masaki, 1987).

2.7. Effect of Polyhouse Structure on Growth and Development of Tomato Plant

Growth and development of tomato plants is influenced by Polyhouse. In this regard a lot of researches have been conducted. In the researches conducted by various scholars, tomato plants grown in rain shelter were relatively longer than those grown in outdoor (Halim and Islam, 2013; Rana *et al.* 2014; Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu, 2017). Similarly, plants grown in rain shelter had more branches than those grown in outdoor (Rana *et al.* 2014; Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu, 2017; Singh, 2018). Tomato plants under plastic shelters have been found to grow higher and better in terms of the number of leaves compared to those without shelters (Latifah *et al.*, 2015). The improved growth and development of the plants could be associated with the suitable environmental conditions prevailed in the polyhouse. In this regard, Cheema *et al.* (2004) and Naik *et al.* (2018) reported that the temperature inside Polyhouse was relatively higher than the temperature outside the polyhouse, which enhance the growth and development of the plants.

Rain shelters or poly houses can influence the phenology of tomato plants, leading to earlier flowering and fruiting compared to open field conditions. Studies have shown that tomato plants grown in polyhouses flowered and bore fruit about 3-8 days earlier than those grown in open fields. This is mainly due to the better microclimate provided by the poly house, such as a relatively higher temperatures in winter months (Ganesan, 2002b; Cheema *et al.*, 2004 ; Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu, 2017).

Tomato plants' first harvest date is affected by the growing conditions. Research by Hadid and Fahim found that tomato plants harvested earlier in a plastic house than in an open field system. This suggests that polyhouse conditions could be beneficial for commercial production of high-value vegetable crops like tomatoes (Hadid & Fahim, 1992; Singh *et al.*, 2011).

2.8. Effect of Polyhouse Structure on Yield and Yield Components of Tomato Plants

In addition to growth parameters, Polyhouse influence the yield and yield parameters of tomatoes. Tomatoes grown in polyhouses have higher yields compared to open field conditions, with a 50% increase reported (Rana *et al.*, 2014). Different tomato varieties have varying yield performances under different growing conditions, with Melkashola performing well under low-cost plastic shelter in Ethiopia. Tomatoes grown under plastic house conditions had the highest marketable yield, with Melkasalsa having the highest yield and Gelilema having the lowest yield. The higher yield in polyhouse-grown tomatoes is attributed to greater fruit number, length, diameter, and weight. This information is supported by studies by Chapagain *et al.* (2014) ; Rana *et al.* (2014); Dessie Getahun (2019); Misganaw Anteneh *et al.* (2021).

Tomato plants protected from rain with a growth structure covered in transparent plastic materials have higher yields per plant and per square meter due to increased photosynthetic activity, resulting in fewer unmarketable fruits. A study by Hakkim (2017) found that protecting tomato plants from rain using plastic shelter produced higher yield per plant. Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu (2017) reported a reduction of unmarketable fruit yield by 18.1% when grown in a plastic rain-shelter structure compared to open field conditions.

Tomato plants grown under polyhouse or rain shelters conditions have been found to produce higher yields of fruits due to increased photosynthetic activity and better environmental conditions, resulting in more flowers and fruits per cluster. According to the research results, polyhouse-grown tomato crops had a higher number of flowers and fruits per cluster

compared to open field conditions. In addition tomatoes grown under low-cost plastic house conditions produced the highest number of flower clusters per plant (Pandey *et al.* 2006; Pramila and Aarya, 2019).

Tomato plants grown in protected structures like rain shelters and plastic houses have been found to produce higher fruit set percentages compared to those grown outdoors. In the researches conducted by various scholars, tomato plants grown in polyhouse produced the higher fruit set percentages. This could be due to the better environmental conditions that contribute to better pollination and resulting in greater fruit set (Omprasad *et al.*, 2018 ; Pramila and Aarya, 2019; Singh *et al.*, 2019).

Protected structures like polyhouse provide a more controlled environment for tomato growth, resulting in higher fruit length, width, and weight compared to open field production. Researches conducted by various scholars has shown that individual tomato fruits grown in polyhouse can be up to 10% bigger in weight than those grown in open fields. Additionally, fruits grown in protected environments have lower acidity levels due to lower photosynthetic activity and carbohydrate accumulation (Sakiyama and Stevens, 1976 ; Parvej, 2010 ; Rana *et al.*, 2014; Meena *et al.*, 2016 ; Ro *et al.*, 2021).

Polyhouse are effective in reducing fruit cracking, fungal and bacterial diseases, and insect attacks in sensitive crops like tomatoes compared to open field production (Kratky, 2006 ; Bottino, 2018). Polyhouse coverings significantly reduce the percentage of cracked tomato fruit by 13.6%. Sweet peppers grown in polyhouses also experienced lower incidence of bacterial wilt (3.08%) and blossom end-rot (4.32%) compared to open field conditions. Additionally, the incidence of thrips was also significantly reduced by 41.44% in protected conditions than open field grown tomatoes (Kratky, 2006; Singh *et al.*, 2011; Malshe *et al.*, 2016; Tian *et al.*, 2019).

Polyhouse has been found to reduce the incidence and severity of late blight in tomatoes, as well as other diseases. According to Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu (2017), tomatoes grown under rain-shelter structures have lower disease incidence (16.7%) and

severity indexes (26.7%) on leaves and as well as on fruits 22.4% and 37.9%, respectively compared to outdoor cultivation (Fig.2.2). This has led some African countries to promote Polyhouse for tomato production during the main rainy season in humid/semi-humid climates (KHDP, 2007; RESCAP, 2011 ; Kelley *et al.*, 2014).

Source: (Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu, 2017)

Figure 2.1. Effect of growth conditions on late blight incidence and severity of tomatoes grown during the rainy season of 2013 in Bahir Dar

The cultivation technology using Polyhouse is important for getting a higher return because of the high yield and quality (Regmi, 2005). Growing tomatoes under plastic shelters during the rainy season would help improve the supply of fresh tomatoes during the rainy season, benefiting growers, consumers, traders and brokers (Pandey and Chaudhary, 2004). This practice of high-yield, good-quality tomato production will allow growers to get a high price from rainy-season tomatoes and improve the supply of fresh tomatoes year-round (Dessie Getahun, 2019). In the researches conducted in Ethiopia by Misganaw Anteneh *et al.* (2021) a total of 32,145 ETB ha⁻¹ was obtained from production of 26.7 t /ha of melkasalsa variety using plastic shelter and 26,366.8 ETB ha⁻¹ from production of 25.53 t/ha of Melkashola variety with shelter as compared to without plastic shelter production system.

Chapter 3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Description of the Study Area

The experiment was conducted during the main rainy season at Koga Irrigation Scheme in 2022/23. Geographically, the study area is located between latitudes 11° 10' N and 11° 25' N and longitudes 37° 02' E and 37° 17' E in the North *Mecha district* of the Amhara region, Ethiopia with an altitude of about 1960 m.a.s.l. (Fig. 3.2). The mean monthly temperature of the study area during the experimental period (August-December) was about 19.0 °C with the mean maximum and minimum temperatures of 28.3 °C and 9.7 °C, respectively, whereas that of rainfall was about 514.5 mm (Ethiopian Meteorology Agency, Bahir Dar Branch). Its slope ranges from nearly flat to 5%.

Koga Irrigation Scheme comprises about 34,000 ha, of which 28,000 ha are within the Koga catchment (Habtamu Tilahun, 2009). Major crops grown in the Koga Irrigation Scheme include Wheat, Barely, Maize, Bean, Cabbage, Potato, Tomato, Onion, Pepper as indicated by Melkamu Alemayehu *et al.* (2015). Vegetable crops that are produced under irrigation in the Koga Irrigation Scheme are Maize, Potato, Onion, Cabbage, Pepper, Tomato and Garlic (Direse Tewabe and Mekete Dessie, 2020) and under open field during summer (Rainy season): Maize, Potato, Onion, (Desale Kidane *et al.*, 2021).

The choice of farmers was based on the strong willingness of farmers. The other criteria for the selection of the farmers were the know-how about the tomato cultivation system for polyhouse tomatoes and those who can contribute materials for the construction of shelters. A total of four farmers were selected from three different *Kebeles*. As part of this research intervention, one farmer from *Kollela Kebele*, two farmers from *Enguti Kebele* and one farmer from *Kudmi Kebeles* in North *Mecha* district were selected.

Figure 3.1. Maximum and minimum Temperatures (°C) and Relative humidity (%) of the study areas during the experimental period (August-December) inside the polyhouse

Figure 3.2: Map of the study Area

3.2. Description of Experimental materials

Three hybrid tomato varieties; Galilea, Galilea-39 and Gabbi were used as experimental materials. Galilea variety was registered in 2011 by Hazera genetics ltd (Green line Trading P.L.C.) (Table 3.1). It has high quality fruit with high yield and wide range of resistances, good for bush and stacking production, adapted for various climates (MoANR, 2016). Galilea-39 variety is a new determinate, high quality Roma type fruit with high yield and powdery mildew resistance, good for bush and staking production, suited to cold climates (EIAR, 2023). Gabbi variety is a new determinate Roma type hybrid tomato with good fruit quality, good yield, long shelf life and good holding at high temperatures. Wide range of resistances including tomato yellow leaf curl virus and tomato apex necrosis virus (EIAR, 2023)

Table 3.1. Description of tomato varieties used for the study

Variety name	Maturity (day)	Average fruit weight (gm)	Altitude requirement's (m.a.s.l.)	Yield (t/ha)		Year of release	Responsible company
				Research field	Farmers field		
Galilea	-	100-170	-	66.6 t/ha	65.9 t/ha	2011	Hazera Genetic Ltd
Gabbi	85	140-160	Up to 2000	101.64 t/ha	86.86 t/ha	2021	Green life PLC (Hazera Seeds Ltd)
Galilea-39	80	100-150	1550-2000	74.81 t/ha	-	2018	Hazera Genetic Ltd

Source: EIAR, (2023); MoANR, (2016).

3.3. Experimental Treatments, and Design

The experiment consisted of three hybrid tomato varieties (Galilea, Gabbi and Galilea-39) laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four replications where shelters were constructed at three locations (Enguti, Kollala and Kudmi) one shelter at each location except Enguti had two shelters.

3.4. Experimental Procedures and Managements

The seedlings of the hybrid varieties were obtained from Roshnara Rose P.L.C. of Oromiya region which were sown on a tray under a shade house. The trial field under the polyhouse was well prepared with human labor before transplanting the seedlings. Finally, raised beds of 20 cm height were prepared for each replication to facilitate drainage. When the seedlings reached at 3-5 leaf stage with approximate height of 15-25 cm, it was transplanted on the plot sizes of 8.5 x 1 m (8.5 m²).

On each experimental row 20 seedlings were planted at the spacing of 100 cm between rows and 50 cm between plants (SNV Project Ethiopia). The gap between plots was 50 cm, which facilitates the freedom of movement of workers. Irrigation was carried out with a watering can at an interval of one day after transplanting until the seedlings were fully established and at an interval of three days after fully established (two weeks of planting) until flowering and at an interval of five days after flowering till the final harvest.

NPS and Urea fertilizer at the rate of 242 kg Kg ha⁻¹ and 100 Kg ha⁻¹ was applied respectively. The total amount of NPS fertilizer was applied during transplanting while the recommended rate of urea was applied in two equal splits. The first half of urea was applied two weeks after transplanting when the seedlings have been established while the remaining half was applied 30 days after transplanting of seedling (Mecha Woreda Agriculture Office Package). Experimental plots were kept free from weeds manually and other cultural practices such as staking, disease and insect pest control were performed according to the recommendation for tomato cultivation (EARO, 2004).

Diseases and insect pests are the major constraints of tomato production in tropical country which result in reduced yield. Powdery mildew, bacterial wilt and white fly created major problem in the present study. Insecticides such as karrate, Redomil gold MZ 68WG and mancozeb were applied. A broad spectrum fungicide, Ridomil-gold MZ 68WG was applied against late blight disease with the concentration of 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ for 5 times to prevent bacterial wilt diseases. Experimental plants were sprayed with broad-spectrum insecticide, namely

Farrate at the concentration of 500 ml ha⁻¹ uniformly to control cut worm and white fly insect pests. Others such as Altracol 32 SC fungicide were applied to prevent powdery mildew diseases at a concentration of 500 ml ha⁻¹ at three times in five days interval.

3.5. Construction of Polyhouse Structures

A Polyhouse structure measuring 20 m x 7 m with a total area of 140 m² was constructed from locally available building materials and covered with white transparent plastic sheets (10 micrometer thickness) to protect experimental plants from rain before planting of the seedlings. The covering polyethylene sheet for a polyhouse is typically UV resistant to protect the plants inside from harmful UV rays. The transparency percentage of the polyethylene sheet is generally around 90-95%, allowing ample sunlight to enter the polyhouse for plant growth while still providing some shade and protection. Local materials such as wood were used to construct polyhouses. The height of the structure was 4 m at the center and its side was 2.5 m high. The side walls were kept open during the day for ventilation and moisture control.

3.6. Data Collection and Analysis

3.6.1. Growth parameters of tomato

Plant height (cm): height of the plants was measured from the ground level to the tip of upper most part of seven randomly selected plants in each plot at first harvest stage. The mean values were computed and used for analysis.

Number of primary branches per plant (count/plant): number of primary branches was recorded by counting the total number of branches that emerged from the main stem from seven randomly selected tomato plants in each plot at first harvest stage and mean values were computed and used for analysis.

Number of secondary branches per plant (count/plant): number of secondary branches was recorded by counting the total number of branches that emerged from the primary

branches from seven randomly selected tomato plants in each plot at first harvest stage and mean values were computed and used for analysis.

3.6.2. Phenology parameters of tomato

Days to 50% flowering (day): the number of days elapsed was counted from date of transplanting up to the date when 50% of the plants in a plot set flowers.

Days to 1st harvest (day): - The number of days elapsed was counted from transplanting to the date when about 75% of the plants in the plot had at least one fruit at pink stage of maturity (about 30 to 60% of the fruit surface is pink).

3.6.3. Yield and yield related parameters of tomato

Number of clusters per plant (count/plant): this was recorded by counting the total number of flower clusters per plant from seven randomly selected plants in each plot at first harvest stage and the mean values were used for further analysis.

Number of flowers per cluster (count/cluster): The number of flowers in the lower, middle and upper clusters of seven randomly taken tomato plants per each plot was tagged and counted at full bloom and the values were used to calculate fruit set percentage.

Number of fruits per cluster (count/cluster): The number of fruits in lower, middle and upper tagged clusters of seven randomly selected tomato plants at 1st harvest stage was counted and the values were used to calculate fruit set percentage.

Fruit set percentage (%): it is the proportion of the number of fruits to the number of flowers per cluster expressed in percentage. It was calculated based on the formula described by Lema Desalegn (2002).

$$\text{Fruit set(\%)} = \frac{\text{NFrPC}}{\text{NFIPC}} \times 100$$

Where NFrPC = Number of fruit per cluster;

NFIPC = Number of flower per cluster

Marketable fruit yield (t/ha): Fruits free from visible damages, crack and sun burn was considered as marketable as indicated by Lemma Dessalegn (2002). Such fruits harvested from each plot were weighed using sensitive balance and expressed in ton per hectare.

Unmarketable fruit yield (%): Diseased, insect pest, cracked, damaged and sun burnt fruits was considered as unmarketable as indicated by Lemma Dessalegn *et al.* (2003). Unmarketable fruits obtained from successive harvest in each plot were weighed with analytical balance in kg and converted into percentage to the total fruit yield.

Total fruit yield (t/ha): The average total yield was obtained by adding marketable and unmarketable fruit yields.

3.6.4. Tomato fruit physical and chemical quality parameters

Fruit diameter (cm): The diameters of seven randomly selected tomato fruits at each harvest were measured using a digital caliper and the mean values were used for further analysis.

Fruit length (cm): The lengths of seven randomly selected tomato fruits at each harvest were measured using a digital caliper and the mean values were used for further analysis.

Individual fruit weight (g): The weights of seven randomly taken fruits at each harvest were weighed with sensitive balance and average values were taken for further analysis.

PH of tomato fruit juice: The juice of three randomly selected fruits from the second harvest was extracted using juice extractor. The aliquot of the juice was filtered with cheese cloth and the pH value of the juice was measured with a pH meter as indicated by Acedo and Thah (2008).

Total soluble solid (^oBrix): An aliquot of juice was extracted from three randomly selected fruits harvested from each plot and 50 ml of the slurry was filtered using cheese cloth. The

TSS was determined by hand refractometer with a range of 0 to 32 °Brix and a resolution of 0.2 °Brix by placing 1 to 2 drops of clear juice on the prism (Alemu Kumlachew *et al.*, 2014).

Titrrtable acidity of fruit juice (%): Aliquot of juice was prepared according to Acedo and Thanh, (2008). The descant clear juice was used for the analysis. Titratable acidity was then determined by titrating 10 ml of tomato juice with 0.01N NaOH and calculated with the following formula.

$$TA(\%) = \frac{\text{Titrex}0.1N\text{NaOHx}0.64}{1000} \times 100$$

Where, TA% = Titratable acidity percentage,

Titre is the volume of tomato juice and 0.1N is the amount of NaOH used to neutralize 0.64 g of citric acid and 0.64 is the conversion factor.

Juice content (%): Three randomly selected fruits from each plot were crashed and their juice was extracted by juice extractor and sieved with three level sieves and the juice content was calculated as follow:

$$\text{Juice content}(\%) = \frac{\text{Total weight of juice} - \text{beaker weight}}{\text{Total weight of fruit}} * 100$$

3.7. Data Analysis

All the collected data were subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Statistical Analysis System (SAS) version 9.4. Variance homogeneity was tested for individual sites using Bartlett's test. Mean separation was carried out using Fisher's Least Significance Difference (LSD) at 5% significance level based on the results of the analysis of variance as indicated by Gomez and Gomez (1984).

3.8. Financial Feasibility Study

Financial feasibility of the investment on Polyhouse for the production of tomato was evaluated by using project evaluation measures. Payback Period (PBP), Benefit Cost Ratio (B/C), Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) were used for project evaluation. Except PBP, which is an undiscounted measure, all others, BCR, NPV and IRR, are discounted measures of the project worthiness (Berry *et al*, 1979; Gittinger, 1982). A discount rate of 18% was used in the present study to estimate these parameters. The selection criterion for the interest rate because the producers can obtain loan at 18% interest rate from Tsedey Bank.

For estimating the cash flows, actual data was used for first year and for the remaining two years the cash flows were extrapolated appropriately based on the current available information.

The PBP was calculated by adding all the Net cash flow of the three years of production. NPV was calculated on MS Excel by using Trigonometric functions at 18% discount rate. The IRR was calculated using MS Excel at 18% interest rate. Benefit cost ratio was calculated by using the formula:

$$BCR = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{B_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t}}$$

Where,

BCR = Benefit cost ratio

B_t = total benefit

C_t = total cost

The discounted factor was calculated by the formula:

$$\text{Discounted factor} = 1 / (1+r)^t$$

Where

r = discount rate

t=year/lifespan of the project

Total cost: It is the sum of fixed and variable costs. It was calculated using the formula:

$$T.C = T.F.C + T.V.C$$

Where, T.F.C=Total fixed cost

T.V.C=Total variable cost

Total return: Total return in the plastic house was calculated through the following formulas

$$\text{Total return} = \text{Total marketable yield (kg)} \times \text{Average price (ETB)}$$

Net income was calculated using the formula below.

$$\text{Net income} = \text{Total return} - \text{Total cost (fixed and variable cost)}$$

3.9. Experimental Soil Sampling and Analysis

Soil samples were collected from four experimental sites at depths up to 20 cm using auger in a diagonal manner from nine randomly selected points. The collected soil samples were composited for individual location. From the composite soil, 1 kg of soil sample was taken and analyzed for selected physio-chemical properties including texture, pH, organic matter, organic carbon, total nitrogen, available P, and CEC in the soil laboratory of the college of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Bahir Dar University using the standard procedures.

To determine organic carbon content of the soils, the Walkley and Black, (1934) method was employed in which the carbon was oxidized under standard conditions with potassium dichromate in a sulfuric acid solution. Total nitrogen was analyzed by Micro-Kjeldhal

digestion method with sulphuric acid (Moreno, 2008). Available phosphorus was determined by the Olsen's method using a spectrophotometer (Olsen *et al.*, 1980). Soil texture analysis was performed by Bouyoucous hydrometer method. Soil pH was measured in water at soil to water ratio of 1:2.5. The CEC was measured after saturating the soil with 1N ammonium acetate (NH₄OAc) and displacing it with 1N NaOH (Basu, 2011).

The results of the soil analysis are indicated in Table 3.2 and Table 3.3. According to USDA soil textural classification system, the soil of the experimental field was classified as Sandy clay loam at Enguti-I, Enguti-II and Kolllela locations and sandy clay at Kudmi location (Table 3.2). The soil pH value of the experimental site was 5.88 at Enguti-I, 5.99 at Enguti-II, 5.6 at Kolllela and 5.45 at Kudmi locations. This indicated that the soil reactions were found to be moderately acidic except Kudmi location which is strongly acidic (Table 3.2).

The total N recorded from the experimental field was 0.31 at Enguti-I, 0.42 at Enguti-II, 0.27 at Kolllela and 0.25 at Kudmi locations (% by weight) where put the value within 0.25-0.42% range as very high rating (Tekalign Tadesse, 1991 and Egata *et al.*, 2016) (Table 3.3). The available P recorded from the experimental site is in the range of 4.62 to 6.6 ppm of surface soil, indicating presence of moderate available P except in Kudmi (London, 1991) (Table 3.3).

The Organic Carbon content of the experimental plot was found to be moderate in the range of 1.59 to 1.85% at all experimental sites (Table 3.3). This moderate Organic Carbon rating indicates that the soil has average structural condition with average structural stability (Olsen *et al.*, 1980).

The Organic Matter content of the experimental field was 2.73% - 3.18% at all tested locations (Table 3.3). According to Walkley and Black (1934), the values of Organic Matter range between 1.70 -3.00% is rated as moderate indicating status of an average structural condition with average structural stability.

Table 3.2. Major soil physical properties of the experimental field before planting in 2022 cropping season at Koga Irrigation Scheme, Northwest, Ethiopia

Physical Properties	Enguti I	Enguti II	Kollela	Kudmi
Sand (%)	54	62	52	54
Silt (%)	18	16	22	12
Clay (%)	28	22	26	34
Textural class	Sandy clay loam	Sandy clay loam	Sandy clay loam	Sandy clay

Table 3.3. Major soil chemical properties of the experimental field before planting in 2022 cropping season at Koga Irrigation Scheme, Northwest, Ethiopia

Locations	Chemical Properties	Content	Rate	Reference
Enguti I	PH (1:2.5 H ₂ O)	5.88	M. acidic	(USDANRCS, 2017)
	Organic carbon (%)	1.73	Moderate	(Olsen <i>et al.</i> , 1982)
	Organic matter (%)	3.0	Moderate	(Tekalign Tadesse , 1991)
	Total Nitrogen (%)	0.31	Very high	(Tekalign Tadesse, 1991)
	Available P (ppm)	6.3	Moderate	(London, 1991)
	CEC meq/100g soil	28.8	High	(Hazelton and Murphy, 2007)
Enguti II	PH (1:2.5 H ₂ O)	5.99	M. acidic	(USDANRCS, 2017)
	Organic carbon (%)	1.85	Moderate	(Olsen <i>et al.</i> , 1982)
	Organic matter (%)	3.18	Moderate	(Tekalign Tadesse, 1991)
	Total Nitrogen (%)	0.32	Very high	(Tekalign Tadesse, 1991)
	Available P (ppm)	5.6	Moderate	(London, 1991)
	CEC meq/100g soil	26.6	High	(Hazelton and Murphy, 2007)
Kollela	PH (1:2.5 H ₂ O)	5.6	M. acidic	(USDANRCS, 2017)
	Organic carbon (%)	1.65	Moderate	(Olsen <i>et al.</i> , 1982)
	Organic matter (%)	2.84	Moderate	(Tekalign Tadesse, 1991)
	Total Nitrogen (%)	0.27	high	(Tekalign Tadesse, 1991)
	Available P (ppm)	6.6	Moderate	(London, 1991)
	CEC meq/100g soil	18.8	Moderate	(Hazelton and Murphy, 2007)
Kudmi	PH (1:2.5 H ₂ O)	5.45	Str. acidic	(USDANRCS, 2017)
	Organic carbon (%)	1.59	Moderate	(Olsen <i>et al.</i> , 1982)
	Organic matter (%)	2.73	Moderate	(Tekalign Tadesse, 1991)
	Total Nitrogen (%)	0.25	High	(Tekalign Tadesse, 1991)
	Available P (ppm)	4.62	Low	(London, 1991)
	CEC meq/100g soil	21.2	Moderate	(Hazelton and Murphy, 2007)

Meq =Milliequivalent, ppm = percent per million.

Chapter 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Growth Parameters of Hybrid Tomato Varieties under Polyhouse Structure

4.1.1. Plant height

The result obtained from the analysis of variance revealed that the tested hybrid tomato varieties differ highly significantly ($P < 0.01$) in their plant height at each experimental site and combined across the locations (Appendix Table 1). Except in Kudmi site, the tallest plant height was recorded from Gabbi variety while the shortest plant height was recorded from Galilea variety, which was in most cases statistical similar with Galilea-39 (Table 4.1).

At Kudmi experimental site the longest plant height was recorded from Galilea-39 variety (176.64 cm) whereas the shortest plant height was recorded from Galilea variety (155.82 cm) which was statistically at par with Gabbi variety (165.00 cm) (Table 4.1). Similarly, from the combined locations, the tallest plant height was recorded from Gabbi variety (174.63 cm) whereas the shortest plant height was recorded from variety Galilea (156.95 cm) (Table 4.1).

As indicated by Rajendran *et al.* (2021), having longer plants in tomato production increased photosynthesis, number of clusters per plant and number of flower per cluster and these may lead to the increment of the productivity. The tallest tomato varieties generally require a long growing season and special management practices such as staking, and may also face the incidence of diseases and insect pests (Alemayehu Seyoum *et al.*, 2016). The difference in plant height among the tested hybrid tomato varieties could be due to genetical differences. The results of this study coincide with the findings of Tejaswini and Geetha (2018), who stated that the significant differences were found for plant height among the hybrid varieties of tomato at maturity stage because of their genetic makeup.

The mean plant height of the tested tomato varieties ranged from 156.95cm to 174.63 cm, which is consistent with the findings of Ramesh *et al.* (2022), who found that the height of tomato plants in sheltered structures ranged from 126.2 cm to 246.31 cm depending on the

environmental conditions and the varieties used. However, the result contradicts with the observations of Meseret Degefa *et al.* (2012), who found that height of tomato crop ranged from 36.80 to 126.7 cm, which may be due to the variety differences.

4.1.2. Number of primary branches per plant

The analysis of variance indicated that the number of primary branches has been influenced by hybrid varieties at each experimental sites and combined across the locations (Appendix Table 1). Except in Kudmi, the highest number of primary branches per plant was counted from Gabbi variety in each location and across all the locations. The lowest number of primary branches per plant was counted from Galilea-39 variety which is statistically similar with Galilea at Enguti I and II and from Galilea variety at Kollala locations which was statistically similar with that of Galilea-39. In Kudmi, the highest number of primary branches of tomatoes was recorded from Galilea (9.20) while the lowest from Gabbi variety (6.80) (Table 4.1).

Primary branches have a direct impact on the economic yield of tomatoes (Shushay Chernet *et al.*, 2013). More number of primary branches per plant enables the formation of a more number of clusters and number flowers per cluster that leads to enhanced fruit production (Husen Yesuf *et al.*, 2022). The observed highest number of primary branches in Gabbi variety could be associated with the increased height of the plants and the genetic makeup of the variety. In this regard, Sharma and Rastogi (1993) reported that there is an increasing tendency in the number of branches with an increase in plant height of tomatoes.

The mean number of primary branches per plant was between 6.90 and 8.60, which are in line with the work of Desalegn Regassa *et al.* (2016), who reported that the number of primary branches per plant ranged from 2.47 to 10.67. However, the present results disagree with the observations of Gupta *et al.* (2017), who found that the number of primary branches per plant of poly house grown tomatoes ranged from 3.35 to 4.33, which could be associated with the environmental conditions, the agronomic practices and the variety used.

4.1.3. Numbers of secondary branches per plant

The analysis of variance revealed that the number of secondary branches has been influenced by tomato varieties in all experimental sites except in Enguti I (Appendix Table 1). Gabbi variety of tomato produced more number of secondary branches per plant at Enguti II and Kolllela experimental sites with a value of 19.32 and 18.54, respectively. On the other hand the lowest number of secondary branches per plant was produced from Galilea-39 (13.64) at Enguti II and from Galilea (12.25) at Kolllela location (Table 4.1).

At Kudmi experimental site, Galilea variety had more number of secondary branches (16.47) per plant while Galilea-39 variety produced the lowest number of secondary branches (11.21) per plant (Table 4.1). Combined over locations, Gabbi variety of tomato produced the highest (17.61) number of secondary branches while Galilea-39 (14.84) recorded the lowest number of secondary branches, which were statistically similar with that of Galilea (15.10) (Table 4.1).

The more number of secondary branches per plant could be due to increased height of the plants, the high number of primary branches and the better response of Gabbi variety to the study area. The results of this study coincide with the findings of Melkamu Alemayehu and Getachew Alemayehu (2017), who reported that there is significant variation in number of branches among tomato varieties that can be associated with the increase of plant height of tomatoes grown in the rain shelter. These conditions create a favorable environment for plant growth and development.

The mean number of secondary branches per plant ranges from 14.86–17.61, which is in line with the work of Habtamu Tegen *et al.* (2016), who found that the number of secondary branches per plant in tomato cultivars ranged from 11.73–31.66 under poly house conditions. However, the result contradicts the findings of Dhyani *et al.* (2017), who reported that the number of secondary branches of hybrid tomato cultivars ranged from 25.46 to 39.23 per plant.

Table 4.1. Selected growth parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North Mecha District

Locations	Tomato varieties	Plant Height (cm)	No. of Primary Branches	No. of Secondary Branches
Enguti I	Galilea	160.89c	7.95b	15.3
	Gabbi	180.54a	9.72a	17.3
	Galilea-39	166.23b	6.89b	16.86
	P-Value	**	**	ns
	LSD (5%)	5.14	0.79	1.51
	SE ±	1.72	0.26	0.44
	CV (%)	1.76	5.74	5.25
Enguti II	Galilea	158.03b	7.32b	15.57b
	Gabbi	178.14a	8.91a	19.32a
	Galilea-39	162.71b	5.80b	13.64c
	P-Value	**	*	***
	LSD (5%)	7.46	0.76	1.25
	SE ±	1.99	0.31	0.36
	CV (%)	2.39	8.57	4.48
Kollela	Galilea	153.05b	7.01b	12.25b
	Gabbi	174.84a	9.07a	18.54a
	Galilea-39	161.36b	7.51b	17.71a
	P-Value	**	*	**
	LSD (5%)	7.82	1.31	2.19
	SE ±	2.13	0.23	0.63
	CV (%)	2.61	5.79	7.84
Kudmi	Galilea	155.82b	9.20a	16.47a
	Gabbi	165.00b	6.80c	15.30b
	Galilea-39	176.64a	7.41b	11.21c
	P-Value	*	*	***
	LSD (5%)	5.57	0.51	0.76
	SE ±	2.74	0.33	0.22
	CV (%)	3.30	8.45	3.08
Combined over location	Galilea	156.95c	7.87b	15.10b
	Gabbi	174.63a	8.60a	17.61a
	Galilea-39	166.74b	6.90c	14.86b
	P-Value	**	**	**
	LSD (5%)	3.41	0.34	0.77
	SE ±	1.02	0.15	0.24
	CV (%)	2.44	7.76	5.94

Means within a column sharing common letter(s) are not significantly different, **=highly significant, * significant, ns=non-significant, LSD=Least Significance Difference, SE=Standard Error, CV=Coefficient of Variation

4.2. Phenological Parameters of Hybrid Tomato Varieties under Polyhouse Structure

4.2.1. Days to 50% flowering

Days to 50% flowering were highly significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced by hybrid varieties at each experimental site as well as over combined locations except in Kollala which was significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced (Appendix Table 2). The variety Galilea required longest days to reach 50% flowering at Enguti I, Enguti II and Kollala locations, which ranged from 37.25 to 42.25 days from transplanting to flowering. On the other hand, at Kudmi, the variety Galilea-39 flowered relatively late (43.25 days) while Gabi variety flowered earlier (35.00 days) (Table 4. 2). The variety Galilea-39 however flowered earlier at Enguti I, Enguti II and Kollala locations within 29.75 to 32.5 days after transplanting which is statistically similar with Gabbi variety at Enguti II and Kollala locations.

Combined across locations, the earliest days to 50% flowering was recorded from Gabbi variety (34.06 days) which is statistically at par with Galilea-39 variety (34.19 day) while the longest days to 50% flowering was recorded from Galilea variety (39.00 day) (Table 4.2).

The differences in days to 50% flowering among the varieties could be due to the differences in genetic makeup of the varieties used in the present study. This idea is in agreement with report of Abdelmageed and Gruda (2009), who explained that the difference in days to 50% flowering could be attributed by the genetic makeup of genotypes.

The prolonged 50% flowering of the variety Galilea-39 at Kudmi site compared to other experimental sites where the variety flowered earlier could be associated with the site of the polyhouse where it was constructed under eucalyptus trees. Obviously the variety requires full sunlight where shading effect caused longer plants (Table 4.1) and prolonged 50% flowering (Table 4.2). Generally, the hybrid tomato varieties used in the present study attained 50% flowering within 34.1 to 39.0 days after transplanting under Polyhouse in the study area. The results of the present study are in line with the findings of Malavika *et al.* (2017) and Ramesh *et al.* (2022), who reported that 50% flowering of tomato varieties under polyhouse

technologies ranged from 17.67 days to 59.31 days, depending on the environmental conditions and the varieties used.

4.2.2. Days to first harvest

Days to first harvest were influenced by variety in all locations as well as combined over the locations (Appendix Table 2). The variety Galilea required the longest days to reach the first harvest at Enguti I and Kollala locations as well as combined across the locations which ranged from 89.56-90.75 days, which is statistically similar to Gabbi variety at Kollala (85.25 days). At Enguti II location, the variety Gabbi (92.00 days) required longest days to reach first harvest. On the other hand, the earliest first harvest was recorded by Galilea-39 variety at Enguti I, Enguti II and Kollala locations as well as combined across the locations, which ranged from 80.00-84.06 days which is statistically similar with Galilea at Enguti II (85.50 days) (Table 4.2).

At kudmi location, the longest days to first harvest was recorded from Galilea-39 variety (94.00 days) which is statistically similar to Galilea variety (91.50 days) while the earliest first harvest was recorded from Gabbi variety (82. 00 days) (Table 4.2).

The differences in days to first harvest among the varieties could be due to the differences in genetic makeup of the varieties used in the present study and the varietal response to the congenial growing environment in polyhouse structures and the early flowering. The results are in agreement with the findings of Prema *et al.* (2011) and Mounica *et al.* (2022), who reported that the early maturity of hybrid tomato varieties is attributed as genotypic character and the early flowering in cherry tomato.

The prolonged first harvest of the variety Galilea-39 at Kudmi site compared to other experimental sites where the variety reached early first harvest could be associated with the site of the polyhouse where it was constructed under eucalyptus trees in Kudmi. Accordingly, the variety Galilea-39 may require full sunlight where shading may cause longer plants (Table 4.1) and prolonged 50% flowering and also prolonged days to first harvest (Table 4.2).

According to Pandey *et al.* (2006), earliness plays an important role on fetching higher market price and more income. Haileslassie Gebremeskel *et al.* (2016) also report that early varieties are generally preferred for cultivation on commercial scale.

Generally, the hybrid tomato varieties used in the present study attained first harvest within 84.06-89.56 days after transplanting under Polyhouse in the study area. The results of the present study are in line with the findings of Omprasad *et al.* (2018), who reported that the average number of days needed for the first fruit harvest ranged from 70 to 98 days under plastic house conditions. However, the result contradict with the findings of Chapagain *et al.* (2012), who reported that days to first harvest of tomato varieties was in the range of 76.50-82.17 days grown under plastic house conditions depending on the variety used. These differences could be associated with differences in the variety used, the environmental conditions and agronomic practices implemented.

Table 4.2. Selected phenological parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North Mecha District

Days to 50% flowering (Day)						Days to first harvest (Day)				
Tomato varieties	Enguti I	Enguti II	Kollela	Kudmi	Over locations	Enguti I	Enguti II	Kollela	Kudmi	Over locations
Galilea	38.00a	42.25a	37.25a	38.50b	39.00a	90.75a	85.50b	90.5a	91.50a	89.56a
Gabbi	35.50b	33.25b	32.50b	35.00c	34.06b	85.25b	92.00a	85.25a	82.00b	86.19b
Galilea-39	32.50c	31.25b	29.75b	43.25a	34.19b	81c	81.25b	80.00b	94.00a	84.06c
P-Value	**	**	*	**	**	*	**	**	**	**
LSD (5%)	2.00	3.83	3.47	2.72	1.48	4.51	4.62	4.24	3.36	2.43
SE ±	0.58	1.11	1.10	0.79	0.50	0.67	1.04	0.99	0.97	0.48
CV (%)	3.27	6.21	6.05	4.04	5.59	1.57	2.40	2.32	2.18	2.23

*Means within a column sharing common letter(s) are not significantly different, **=highly significant,* significant, LSD=Least Significance Difference, SE=Standard Error, CV=Coefficient of Variation, C. Mean=Combined Mean.*

4.3. Yield and Yield related Parameters of Hybrid Tomato Varieties under Polyhouse Structure

4.3.1. Number of flower clusters per plant

The analysis of variance indicated that the number of flower cluster per plant was highly significantly ($p < 0.01$) influenced by hybrid tomato varieties at each location and combined across the locations (Appendix Table 3). At Enguti I (34.43), Enguti II (29.75) and Kollala (34.45) locations, Gabbi variety of tomato produced the highest number of flower clusters per plant while variety Galilea recorded the lowest number of flower cluster per plant at Enguti I (25.61) and Kollala (19.28) locations and Galilea-39 at Enguti II (21.81) which is statistically similar with Galilea 39 at Enguti I as indicated in Table 4.3. On the other hand, at Kudmi experimental site the highest number of flower clusters per plant (28.29) was counted from Galilea variety while the variety Gabbi produced the lowest number of flower cluster per plant (18.07). Combined over locations, the highest number of flower cluster per plant was counted from Gabbi variety (29.17), whereas the lowest number of flower cluster per plant was counted from Galilea variety (25.01) which is statistically similar to variety Galilea-39 (25.59) (Table 4.3).

As indicated by Pandey *et al.* (2006), the number of flower clusters per plant is one of the major parameters for selecting tomato varieties for specific area of production and it determines the yielding potentials of that particular variety. The difference in number of flower cluster per plant among the tested tomato varieties in the present study could be associated with the genetic potentials of the varieties. In this regard, the highest number of flower cluster at Enguti I, Enguti II and Kollala might be associated with longest plant heights, presence of more number of primary and secondary branches in the variety Gabbi as indicated in the present study. This could be in turn associated with better adaptation of the variety to the environmental conditions in the polyhouse structures. The same is also true for Galilea variety at Kudmi where it recorded more primary and secondary branches and higher flower cluster per plant. Gabbi variety produced less flower cluster in Kudmi due to the less

adaptation of the variety to shading effect as the polyhouse was constructed under the shade of eucalyptus tree.

The tested hybrid tomato varieties produced on the average about 25.01 to 29.17 flower cluster per plant across the location, which is in line with the findings of Chapagain *et al.* (2012) and Pandey *et al.* (1970), who reported the number of flower cluster of tomatoes grown in plastic house in the range of 18.07 - 34.45 and 17.23 - 36.23, respectively. The results of the present study are also in accordance with the findings of Sumathi *et al.* (2013a) in poly house tomato and Prema *et al.* (2011) in cherry tomato who reported that tomato crops grown under poly house conditions produced higher number of flower cluster as response to the favorable micro climate.

4.3.2. Number of flowers per cluster

The analysis of variance showed that the number of flowers per cluster was highly significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced by hybrid tomato varieties at Enguti I, Enguti II and combined across the locations (Appendix Table 3). At Enguti I (7.36), Enguti II (6.86) and combined locations (6.68), Gabbi variety of tomato produced the highest number of flowers per cluster which is statistically similar with that of Galilea 39 at Enguti I. On the other hand, variety Galilea record the lowest number of flowers per cluster at Enguti I (5.95) and Galilea-39 recorded the lowest number of flower per cluster at Enguti II (5.06) and combined across the locations (6.06) which is statistically similar with the variety Galileaas indicated in Table 4.3.

At Kudmi experimental site, the highest number of flowers per cluster (7.01) was recorded from Galilea variety while the variety Gabbi produced the lowest number of flowers per cluster (5.39), which is statistically comparable to the variety Galilea-39 (6.07) (Table 4.3).

As indicated by Abdelmageed *et al.* (2003), the increased production of flowers on tomato plant means high probability in fruit set percentage that may lead to higher yield. A higher number of flowers per cluster could result in greater fruit set percentage in a given hybrid variety under favorable agro climatic conditions. Varying number of flowers per cluster

among the varieties was also reported by Cheema *et al.* (2013) and Hossain *et al.* (2014) in tomato hybrids. The difference in number of flowers per cluster among the tested tomato varieties in the present study could be associated with the genetic potentials of the varieties. Similar results were obtained by Parvej *et al.* (2010) in poly house tomato and Prema *et al.* (2011) in cherry tomato. Aquirre and Cabrera (2012) and Muthuvel *et al.*(2000) also reported that the number of inflorescence and stigma exertion are inherent characters.

The tested hybrid tomato varieties produced on the average about 6.07 to 6.68 flowers per cluster across the locations, which are in line with the findings of Cheema *et al.* (2013), who found that the number of flowers per cluster of tomato varieties in the protected structure ranged from 5.00 to 10.00. However, these results did not agree with the observation of Meseret Degefa *et al.* (2012) where they found less flowers per cluster (2.27 to 5.89) in different tomato varieties that may be due to the varieties used and the agronomic practices implemented.

4.3.3. Number of fruits per cluster

The analysis of variance revealed that hybrid tomato varieties highly significantly ($P<0.01$) influenced the number of fruits per cluster at all locations as well as combined over locations except in Enguti II (Appendix Table 3). Accordingly, the variety Gabbi produced the highest number of fruits per cluster at Enguti I (5.29) and at Kollala sites (6.01). On the other hand, the lowest number of fruits per cluster was produced by the variety Galilea at Enguti I (3.93) and Kollala (3.83) locations as indicated in Table 4.3.

At Kudmi location however, the variety Galilea produced the highest number of fruits per cluster (5.34) while the variety Gabbi (3.42) produced the lowest number of fruits per cluster (Table 4.3). Combined over locations, the variety Gabbi produced the highest number of fruits per cluster (5.00) while Galilea variety (4.47) produced the lowest number of fruits per cluster, which was statistically similar with that of Galiea-39 variety (4.58) (Table 4.3).

Number of fruits per cluster is one of the major criteria to select better variety for yield and fruit set percent in tomatoes. Generally, the variety Gabbi performed well in the three locations (Enguti I, Enguti II and Kollala) in terms of the number of fruits per cluster, which is associated obviously with genetically high yielding potential of the variety. In contrary, the same variety produced the lowest number of fruits per cluster in Kudmi site, which is associated with the shade effects of the eucalyptus tree where the polyhouse was constructed. This indicates that the variety Gabbi requires full sunlight to express its yielding potentials compared to other varieties. On the other hand, the variety Galilea performed well in eucalyptus shaded polyhouse (Kudmi site) in terms of fruit number per cluster, which indicates the shade tolerance of the variety.

The tested tomato varieties generally produced 4.5-5.0 fruits per cluster across the locations, which are in agreement with the findings of Yebrzaf Yesiwas *et al.* (2016), who reported that the number of fruits per cluster of tomato varieties under greenhouse conditions in Ethiopia ranged from 4.75 to 6.84.

4.3.4. Fruit set percentage

The result obtained from the analysis of variance revealed that fruit set percentage has not been influenced by tomato varieties in all experimental sites except in Kudmi (Appendix Table 3). at Kudmi location the highest fruit set percentage was recorded from Galilea variety (76.36%) which is statistically at par with variety Galilea-39 (74.60%) whereas the lowest fruit set percentage was recorded from variety Gabbi (63.52%) (Table 4.3).

The difference in fruit set percentage among the tested tomato varieties in the present study could be associated with the genetic makeup of the varieties. The results obtained in the present study are in line with the findings of Prema *et al.* (2011) in cherry tomato.

The tested tomato varieties generally produced 73.48 to 76.0% across the four locations in the present study (Table 4.3), which is consistent with the reports of Pandey *et al.* (1970). According to the author the average fruit set percentage for tomato varieties grown under

plastic houses ranged from 83.1 to 93.89%. However, on the contrary with the observations of Pramila and Aarya (2019), who reported that the fruit set percentage of tomato varieties under poly house conditions ranged from 33.78% to 53.00%, which is very low compared to the results of the present study.

Table 4.3. Selected yield related parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North *Mecha* District

Locations	Tomato varieties	No. of flower cluster per plant	No. of flower per cluster	No. of fruits per cluster	Fruit set percentage (%)
Enguti I	Galilea	25.61b	5.95b	3.93c	66.03
	Gabbi	34.43a	7.36a	5.29a	72.07
	Galilea-39	27.75b	6.82a	4.82b	70.77
	P-Value	**	**	***	ns
	LSD (5%)	2.23	0.54	0.25	6.03
	SE ±	0.65	0.14	0.07	1.76
	CV (%)	4.41	4.05	3.07	5.05
Enguti II	Galilea	26.86b	6.15b	4.78b	77.79
	Gabbi	29.75a	6.86a	5.29a	77.24
	Galilea-39	21.86c	5.06c	4.18b	82.64
	P-Value	**	**	ns	ns
	LSD (5%)	2.48	0.55	0.61	7.92
	SE ±	0.72	0.16	0.18	2.29
	CV (%)	5.47	5.27	7.49	5.78
Kollela	Galilea	19.28c	5.21b	3.83c	73.69b
	Gabbi	34.45a	7.15a	6.01a	84.10a
	Galilea-39	28.36b	6.28a	4.79b	76.30ab
	P-Value	**	ns	**	ns
	LSD (5%)	4.03	0.98	0.72	8.06
	SE ±	1.16	0.28	0.21	2.33
	CV (%)	8.51	9.11	8.5	5.97
Kudmi	Galilea	28.29a	7.01a	5.34a	76.36a
	Gabbi	18.07c	5.39b	3.42c	63.52b
	Galilea-39	24.39b	6.07b	4.53b	74.60a
	P-Value	**	ns	**	**
	LSD (5%)	1.75	0.78	0.5	4.5
	SE ±	0.51	0.23	0.15	1.30
	CV (%)	4.29	7.36	6.59	3.64
Over locations	Galilea	25.01b	6.06b	4.47b	73.48
	Gabbi	29.17a	6.68a	5.00a	74.23
	Galilea-39	25.59b	6.08b	4.58b	76.08
	P-Value	**	**	**	ns
	LSD (5%)	1.77	0.4	0.3	3.06
	SE ±	0.49	0.10	0.08	1.00
	CV (%)	7.40	6.50	6.48	5.38

Means within a column sharing common letter(s) are not significantly different, **=highly significant, * significant, ns=non significant, LSD=Least Significance Difference, SE=Standard Error, CV=Coefficient of Variation.

4.3.5. Marketable fruit yield

The three hybrid tomato varieties significantly ($P < 0.05$) differ in their marketable fruit yield at each experimental sites and combined across the locations except in Kudmi which is highly significant ($p < 0.01$) (Appendix Table 4.3). Except in Kudmi the variety Gabbi recorded the highest marketable fruit yield in all the three experimental sites (Enguti I (103.07 t/ha), Enguti II (90.75 t/ha) and Kollala (96.19 t/ha)). On the other hand, the variety Galilea in Enguti I (77.74 t/ha) and Kollala locations (85.46 t/ha) and Galilea-39 variety in Enguti II (81.22 t/ha) recorded the lowest marketable fruit yield (84.43 t/ha) which is statistically similar with Galilea-39 at Engiti I and Kollala and with that of Galilea variety at Enguti II (Table 4.4).

At Kudmi experimental site on the other hand, the highest marketable fruit yield was obtained from Galilea variety (87.65 t/ha) which is statistically similar with that of Galilea-39 (83.79 t/ha) variety while the lowest marketable fruit yield was obtained from Gabbi variety (66.43 t/ha) (Table 4. 4). Moreover, from combined analysis of variance the highest marketable fruit yield was obtained from Gabbi variety (89.11 t/ha) whereas the lowest marketable fruit yield was obtained from Galilea and Galilea -39 varieties with the values of 82.63 t/ha and 83.67 t/ha, respectively (Table 4.4).

Marketable fruit yield is the major determinant variable for selection of a particular tomato variety, as it directly affects commercialization and thus income generation of the farmers (Pandey *et al.*, 2006). In this regard, the tested tomato varieties differ in their yielding potential which might be due to their genetic makeup and environmental conditions. The variety Gabbi performed well in Enguti I and II and in Kollala experimental sites. However, its performance was reduced in Kudmi site which is obviously associated with the shading effect of the eucalyptus tree where the polyhouse structure was constructed. The results clearly showed that this variety requires full sunlight to express its yielding potential.

Under shade conditions or limited sunshine, the variety Galilea performed well as indicated at Kudmi experimental site, which indicates the shade tolerance of this variety. Moreover, the

marketable fruit yield was relatively lower at the Kudimi site compared to the other experimental locations. The reason could be associated with unsuitable site selection where the shelter was constructed under the shade of eucalyptus trees. Such conditions obviously reduce the sunlight intensity and thus photosynthesis activities of the plants. In addition, the soil of the experimental site is sandy clay and strongly acidic (Table 3.1) which is not suitable for the production of tomatoes due to less availability of phosphorus and certain micronutrients for plant uptake (Lemma Dessalegn, 2002).

The mean marketable fruit yield of tomato varieties obtained ranged between 82.63 and 89.11 t/ha across the four locations in the present study (Table 4.4), which is in line with the work of Pandey *et al.* (2006), who reported that the average marketable fruit yield of tomato cultivars grown under plastic house conditions during the wet season ranged from 51.98 t/ha to 89.05 t/ha. The marketable yields of tomatoes obtained in the present study were much higher compared to the results of Dessie Getahun (2019), who reported that the average marketable fruit yield of tomato varieties under the Low Cost Plastic Shelter production system in Ethiopia is between 32.58 t/ha and 60.74 t/ha.

The increased marketable fruit yield across the locations in the present study was positively and significantly associated with the number of flower cluster per plant and number of fruits per cluster of hybrid tomato varieties as indicated in Fig. 4.1.

Figure 4.1. Relationship of the number of flower cluster per plant and fruits per cluster (X) with marketable yield of tomato (Y) as affected by hybrid tomato varieties

4.3.6. Unmarketable fruit yield

The analysis of variance revealed that unmarketable fruit yield was very highly significantly ($p < 0.01$) influenced by tomato varieties at Enguti I, Kollala and combined across the locations while it was highly significantly influenced ($p < 0.01$) at Enguti II and Kudmi locations (Appendix Table 3). Except in Enguti II, the variety Galilea-39 recorded the highest unmarketable fruit yield in all the three experimental sites (Enguti I (3.64%), Kollala (3.97%) and Kudmi (1.59%)) as well as combined across the locations (2.67%). On the other hand, the variety Galilea recorded the lowest unmarketable fruit yield at Enguti I (0.39%) and Kudmi (0.69%) while Gabbi variety recorded the lowest unmarketable yield combined across the locations (1.34 %) (Table 4.4).

At Enguti II experimental site on the other hand, the highest unmarketable yield was obtained from Galilea variety (3.96%) while the lowest unmarketable fruit yield was obtained from Galilea-39 variety which is statistically similar with variety Gabbi (1.45%) (Table 4.4).

The difference in unmarketable fruit yield between the varieties might be associated with the genetic makeup of the varieties where Galilea-39 variety was relatively sensitive to diseases and physiological disorders such as blossom end rot, bleaching, and sunken shaped fruits, which may increase the proportion of the unmarketable yield of this variety. The results are in agreement with the work of Milkinesh Tujuba and Negash Geleta (2020), who reported that diseases and insect pests are the major constraints of tomato production in Ethiopia, which may lead to the increased unmarketable yield.

4.3.7. Total fruit yield

Hybrid varieties of tomatoes differed in their total fruit yield in each location and across the locations (Appendix Table 3). Except in Kudmi, the variety Gabbi recorded the highest total fruit yield in all the three experimental sites (Enguti I (104.31 t/ ha), Enguti II (92.20 t/ha) and at Kollala (97.29 t/ha)). On the other hand Galilea variety at Enguti I (78.85 t/ha), Kollala

locations (82.18 t/ha) and Galilea-39 variety (82.56 t/ha) at Enguti II experimental site recorded the lowest total fruit yield (Table 4. 4).

At Kudmi experimental site on the other hand, the highest total fruit yield was obtained from Galilea variety (88.26 t/ha) which is statistically similar with that of Galilea-39 (85.05 t/ha) variety while the lowest total fruit yield was obtained from Gabbi variety (67.58 t/ha) (Table 4). Moreover, over combined across the locations the highest total fruit yield was recorded from Gabbi variety (90.32 t/ha) which is statistically similar with that of Galilea-39 (86.01 t/ha) whereas the lowest total fruit yield was recorded from Galilea variety (84.22 t/ha) which is statistically at par with that of Galilea-39 (86.01 t/ha) (Table 4.4).

The difference in total fruit yield in the present study might be due to the genetic makeup of the variety, which is associated with the presence of a larger number of effective primary and secondary branches, the cumulative effect of a larger number of flowers and fruit per cluster; higher fruit set, longer plant and highest marketable fruit compared to the other varieties. The results are in harmony with the findings of Parvej *et al.* (2010), who reported that the yield of tomato crop grown under polyhouse was due to the taller plants and much number of branches, higher number of flowers and fruits. This study showed that, the variety Gabbi performed well in Enguti I and II and in Kollala experimental sites. However, its performance was reduced in Kudmi site which is obviously associated with the shading effect of the eucalyptus tree where the polyhouse structure was constructed.

The mean total fruit yield of tomato varieties combined over the locations in the present study ranged from 84.22 t/ha to 90.32 t/ha which is consistent with the work of Sasirekha *et al.* (2018), who reported that the total fruit yield of tomato varieties ranged from 61.05-97.02 t/ha as influenced by different protected structures. The result also coincides with the work of Chapagain *et al.* (2018), who reported that the total fruit yield of tomato varieties ranged from 71.4 t/ha-105.8 t/ha under plastic house conditions depending in the varieties used.

Table 4.4. Fruit yield performance of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure in different locations of North Mecha District

Locations	Tomato varieties	Marketable yield (t/ha)	Unmarketable yield (t/ha)	Unmarketable yield (%)	Total yield (t/ha)
Enguti I	Galilea	77.74b	0.31c	0.39c	78.05c
	Gabbi	103.07a	1.24b	1.20b	104.31a
	Galilea-39	84.25b	3.18a	3.64a	87.43b
	P-Value	*	***	***	*
	LSD (5%)	10.44	0.46	0.46	9.33
	SE ±	3.02	0.13	0.13	2.98
	CV (%)	6.83	10.74	10.74	6.64
Enguti II	Galilea	84.43b	3.96a	3.96a	88.39a
	Gabbi	90.76a	1.45b	1.45b	92.20a
	Galilea-39	81.22b	1.34b	1.34b	82.56b
	P-Value	*	**	**	*
	LSD (5%)	4.38	0.32	0.37	4.58
	SE ±	1.27	0.09	0.09	1.32
	CV (%)	2.96	8.2	8.2	3.02
Kollela	Galilea	80.67b	1.50b	1.82b	82.18c
	Gabbi	96.19a	1.09c	1.12c	97.29a
	Galilea-39	85.46b	3.52a	3.97a	88.98b
	P-Value	*	***	***	*
	LSD (5%)	6.44	0.4	0.59	6.34
	SE ±	1.86	0.17	0.07	1.83
	CV (%)	4.26	10.56	10.56	4.09
Kudmi	Galilea	87.65a	0.61c	0.69b	88.26a
	Gabbi	66.43b	1.07b	1.53a	67.50b
	Galilea-39	83.78a	1.29a	1.59a	85.05a
	P-Value	**	**	**	**
	LSD (5%)	7.24	0.18	0.23	7.31
	SE ±	2.09	0.05	0.05	2.12
	CV (%)	5.27	10.23	10.55	5.26
Over locations	Galilea	82.63b	1.59b	1.72b	84.22b
	Gabbi	89.11a	1.21c	1.34c	90.32a
	Galilea-39	83.67b	2.33a	2.67a	86.01b
	P-Value	*	***	***	*
	LSD (5%)	4.5	0.19	0.26	4.42
	SE ±	1.15	0.07	0.17	1.16
	CV (%)	5.42	15.47	7.64	5.33

Means within a column sharing common letter(s) are not significantly different, ***=Very highly significant, **=highly significant, *=significant, LSD=Least Significance Difference, SE=Standard Error, CV=Coefficient of Variation, C. Mean=Combined Mean.

4.4. Fruit Physical and Chemical Quality Parameters of Hybrid Tomato Varieties under Polyhouse Structure

4.4.1. Fruit length

In the present study, the difference between hybrid varieties was significant on the fruit length at each experimental site and combined over locations except in Kollala location (Appendix Table 4). At Enguti I (7.15cm) and Enguti II (7.08 cm), the longest fruit length was recorded from Galilea variety whereas Galilea-39 recorded the shortest fruit length at both locations with the values of 6.14 cm and 6.18 cm respectively (Table 4. 5). At Kudmi sites and combined over locations however, Gabbi variety of tomato recorded the longest fruit while Galilea-39 variety recorded the shortest fruit in terms of length (Table 4. 5).

Fruit length is an important parameter of tomato varieties, which influence customer preferences (Meneberu *et al.*, 2011). The difference in fruit length might be due to the genetic makeup of the hybrid varieties. In this regard, Khapte *et al.* (2018) and Mounica *et al.* (2022), reported that the fruit length of tomato varieties grown in greenhouse ranged from 4.33 to 7.28 cm, which differs with the type of varieties used. Similarly, the average fruit length combined over locations in the present study was ranged between 5.94 cm to 6.83 cm (Table 4.5).

4.4.2. Fruit diameter

The tested hybrid tomato varieties differed highly significantly ($P < 0.01$) in fruit width at Enguti II, Kollala and combined over the locations (Appendix Table 4). The variety Galilea recorded the longest fruit diameter in Enguti II (5.85 cm), Kollala (6.06 cm) as well as combined across the locations (6.03cm). On the other hand, the variety Gabbi recorded the shortest fruit diameter at Enguti II (5.83 cm), and Kollala (5.17 cm) and over combined locations (5.08 cm) which is statistically similar with that of Galilea-39 variety (5.36 cm) across the locations (Table 4.5).

The variation in fruit diameter of such tomato hybrids might be due to the genetic makeup of the hybrids and governed by the cell size and intercellular space of the flesh. These results of this study are in line with the findings of Prema *et al.* (2011) in cherry tomato.

The mean fruit diameter of the hybrids in the present study ranged between 5.08 cm to 6.03 cm across the four locations, which is in line with the results of Yebrzaf Yeshiwas *et al.* (2016) who found the fruit diameter of tomato cultivars ranged from 4.75 cm to 6.25 cm under greenhouse condition depending on the variety used. The result of this study also on conformity with the work of Khapte *et al.* (2018), who reported the fruit diameter of tomato cultivars ranged from 4.67 cm to 7.35 cm under greenhouse conditions. However, the study contradicts with the findings of Chapagain *et al.* (2012b), who found the fruit diameter of tomato varieties under plastic houses ranged from 4.04 cm to 5.78 cm depending on the variety used.

4.4.3. Individual fruit weight

The analysis of variance indicated that individual fruit weight was influenced by hybrid tomato varieties at all locations and combined over locations except in Kudmi (Appendix Table 4). At Engiti I (129.48 g), Enguti II (129.98 g) and Kollala (137.42 g), the variety Galilea produced the heaviest fruit which is statistically similar with Gabbi variety at Enguti II location. Gabbi variety in Enguti I (113.45 g), Galilea-39 variety in Enguti II (113.57 g) and Kollala (115.79 g) locations produced the smallest fruit weight (Table 4.5). Combined over locations Galilea variety (130.60 g) recorded the heaviest fruit while Galilea-39 variety (116.18 g) produced the smallest fruits (Table 4.5).

The variation in individual fruit weight observed in the present study might be due to the genetic makeup of the varieties, which is in line with the findings of other scholars who observed differences in fruit weight of tomato varieties (Cheema *et al.*, 2013; Yebrzaf Yeshiwas *et al.*, 2016; Dhyani *et al.*, 2017).

The mean individual fruit weight of tomato varieties combined over the location in the present study ranged from 116.18 g to 130.60 g, which is in agreement with the observations of Yebrzaf Yeshiwas *et al.* (2016). According to the authors the average fruit weight of tomato varieties grown under greenhouse conditions ranged from 94.72 to 139.20 g, which varies with the varieties used. On the other hand, the individual fruit weight of tomatoes in the present study was much higher than the one observed by Cheema *et al.* (2013) and Dhyani *et al.* (2017) where they recorded the fruit weight of 35.00 g to 72.50 g and 62.50 to 106.74 g, respectively. This difference could be associated with the varieties used, agronomic practices, soil fertility status and etc.

Table 4.5. Selected Physical quality parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North *Mecha* District

Locations	Tomato varieties	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit width (cm)	Individual fruit weight (g)
Enguti I	Galilea	7.15a	6.21	129.48a
	Gabbi	6.84a	5.1	113.45c
	Galilea-39	6.14b	5.77	122.62b
	P-Value	*	ns	**
	LSD (5%)	0.42	0.40	5.10
	SE ±	0.11	0.24	1.47
	CV (%)	3.33	8.35	2.42
Enguti II	Galilea	7.08a	5.83a	129.98a
	Gabbi	6.64b	4.85c	122.06a
	Galilea-39	6.18c	5.35b	113.07b
	P-Value	**	**	*
	LSD (5%)	0.33	0.44	10.32
	SE ±	0.09	0.09	1.86
	CV (%)	2.62	3.25	3.06
Kollela	Galilea	6.24	6.06a	137.42a
	Gabbi	7.16	5.17c	126.49ab
	Galilea-39	5.69	5.64b	115.79b
	P-Value	ns	*	**
	LSD (5%)	0.36	0.37	9.17
	SE ±	0.28	0.11	2.65
	CV (%)	8.74	3.76	4.18
Kudmi	Galilea	6.62a	6.01	125.53
	Gabbi	6.69a	5.19	121.52
	Galilea-39	5.75b	4.66	113.23
	P-Value	*	ns	ns
	LSD (5%)	0.40	0.40	8.20
	SE ±	0.10	0.27	2.37
	CV (%)	3.30	10.16	3.95
Over locations	Galilea	6.77a	6.03a	130.60a
	Gabbi	6.83a	5.08b	120.88b
	Galilea-39	5.94b	5.36b	116.18c
	P-Value	**	**	**
	LSD (5%)	0.13	0.18	4.05
	SE ±	0.08	0.10	1.20
	CV (%)	4.75	7.14	3.93

Means within a column sharing common letter(s) are not significantly different, **=highly significant, * significant, LSD=Least Significance Difference, SE=Standard Error, CV=Coefficient of Variation, C. Mean=Combined Mean.

4.4.4. Fruit juice content

The analysis of variance revealed that fruit juice content was influenced by tomato varieties at all locations and combined over locations except in Kolllela (Appendix Table 5). Galilea variety in Enguti I (87.90%) and Enguti II (79.01%) and Galilea-39 variety in Kolllela (90.16%) and combined over locations (82.68%) produced fruits with the highest juice content. On the other hand, the variety Gabbi produced fruits with the lowest juice content in all locations where the juice content of Gabbi variety in Kolllela was statistically similar with that of Galilea variety and Galilea-39 variety at Enguti I. Similarly the fruits of Gabbi variety (75.95%) had the lowest juice content combined over locations compared to other varieties (Table 4.6).

Juice content of tomato fruits is an important parameter for the selection of varieties for different purposes (Masho Aklile *et al.*, 2016). The differences in fruit juice content among tomatoes observed in the present study are obviously associated with the genetic makeup of the varieties and the environmental conditions of the study areas. Generally, combined over locations the variety Galilea has relatively high juice content compared to other varieties, which makes the variety suitable for agro-processing industry. In this regard, Moreno *et al.* (2009) and Masho Aklile *et al.* (2016) reported that tomatoes with high juice content are preferred for the production of tomato juices in agro-processing industry. Gabbi variety with relatively low juice content in the present study can be used for fresh market as indicated by Masho Aklile *et al.* (2016).

4.4.5. PH of tomato juice

The result of the present study showed that hybrid varieties influenced the pH value of juices at each experimental site as well as over combined locations except in Kolllela location (Appendix Table 5). Galilea variety recorded the highest pH value at (Enguti I (5.57), Enguti II (4.93), and Kudmi (5.28). On the other hand, Galilea-39 variety had the lowest pH value at Enguti II (4.10), Kolllela (4.18) and Kudmi (3.88) locations which is in most cases statistically similar to Gabbi variety. At Enguti I the lowest pH was recorded from Gabbi variety (4.62)

which is statistically at par with Galilea-39 variety (4.64) (Table 4.6). Moreover, over combined locations the highest pH value was recorded from Galilea variety (5.14) while the lowest pH value was recorded with that of Galilea-39 (4.32) which is statistically similar with the variety Gabbi (4.36) (Table 4.6).

pH value determines the flavor and sourness of the juices made from tomato fruit. The difference among the tested varieties in pH value might be due to the genetic makeup of a variety also determines the pH of the fruits and thus the flavor and sourness of the fruits (Ram, 2005). In this regard, Low pH values of tomato juice could be associated with high fruit quality which is accounted to the flavor and sourness of the fruits. The findings of this study are generally in agreement with the findings of Caliman *et al.* (2010) where tomato fruit juices were categorized as acidic with the pH value generally less than 5.

The average pH value combined over locations in the present study was between 4.32-5.14 these values are in line with those obtained by Hazarika and Phookan (2005), who reported that pH values of tomatoes cultivars of tomato fruits grown under controlled environmental condition ranged from 3.56-5.33, because fruit pH affect the time nutrition and genotype.

4.4.6. Total soluble solid of fruit juice

The analysis of variance revealed that TSS was highly significantly ($p < 0.01$) influenced by tomato varieties at Enguti I and over combined across the locations and significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced at Enguti II, Kollala and Kudmi locations (Appendix Table 5). At Enguti I (4.94 °Brix) and Kudmi (4.63 °Brix) locations the highest TSS was recorded from Galilea variety where the variety Galilea was statistically similar with that of Gabbi at Kudmi while the lowest TSS (4.07 °Brix) was recorded from Gabbi variety at Enguti I and Galilea-39 variety (3.82 °Brix) at Kudmi experimental site (Table 4.6). On the other hand however, Galilea-39 variety recorded the highest TSS at Enguti II (5.60 °Brix) and Kollala locations (5.00 °Brix) and over combined across the locations (4.95 °Brix) while the lowest TSS was recorded from Galilea variety (4.93 °Brix) at Enguti II and from Gabbi variety (4.08 °Brix) at Kollala and over combined across the locations (4.85 °Brix) (Table 4.6).

The TSS and TA contents of fruit is one of the major criterion's in selecting of tomato variety for fresh market as it determines the sugar and acid content of a fruit that influences the overall flavor of the fruit (Stevens *et al.*, 1977). Varieties/hybrids with higher TSS levels are better suited for preparing processed products such as tomato powder, canned goods, ketchup, sauce and chutney. TSS is desirable to achieve a higher yield of processed products (Singh *et al.*, 2020). The differences in total soluble solids might be due to differences in genotypes and environmental conditions prevailing during the growing seasons. Significant variability between tomato genotypes for this trait has also been observed by many previous researchers (Meena and Bahadur, 2015; Mitul *et al.*, 2016; Rai *et al.*, 2016; Prakash *et al.*, 2019).

The average TSS values combined over locations in the present study was between 4.25 °Brix to 4.95 °Brix, which is in line with the findings of Purkayastha and Mahanta (2011) reported a similar range of total soluble solids content (3.6–5.4 °Brix) in tomatoes depending on the varieties used. The result also coincide with the work of Waiba *et al.* (2021), who reported that the TSS of tomato cultivars under sheltered growing conditions ranged from 3.76 to 6.53 °Brix. However the result of this study contradicts with the results of Chapagain *et al.* (2018), who found that the TSS of tomato cultivars under plastic houses ranged from 4.82 °Brix to 5.22 °Brix.

4.4.7. Titratable acidity of fruit juice

The analysis of variance of this study showed a highly significant ($p < 0.01$) fruit titratable acidity differences among hybrid tomato varieties at Enguti I, Kolllela and Kudmi locations and very highly significantly ($p < 0.01$) differ at Enguti II and over combined locations (Appendex Table 5). The highest titratable acidity was obtained from Galilea variety at Enguti I (1.10 %), Kolllela (0.98%) and Kudmi (0.48%) and over combined locations (0.84%). The variety Gabbi recorded the lowest titratable acidity at Enguti I (0.52 %), Enguti II (0.57%) and Kolllela (0.72%) locations and over combined locations (0.56%) and Galilea-39 variety (0.42%) recorded the lowest titratable acidity at Kudmi location (Table 4.6). On the other hand, at Enguti II the highest titratable acidity (0.97) was obtained from Galililea-39 variety (Table 4.6).

The difference in the titratable acidity of the fruits in the present study could be obviously due to the genetic difference of the varieties. The lower titratable acidity of the fruits grown in the present study could be a result of the lower rate of photosynthetic activity of the plant and less carbohydrate accumulation in the fruits in the polyhouses due to the lower light intensity level inside the polyhouses as compared to the outdoor. The result is in agreement with the report of Meseret (2010).

The average titratable acidity over combined locations of this study is between the range of 0.56% to 0.84%, which is in line with the work of Chapagain *et al.* (2012a), who reported that the titratable acidity of tomato varieties under plastic housing conditions ranged from 0.495% to 0.903%. However, the result disagrees with the findings of Yebrzf Yesiwas *et al.* (2016), who found that the titratable acidity of tomato varieties ranged from 0.12% to 0.24% under greenhouse conditions. The result also contradicts with the work of Singh *et al.* (2020) who reported that the performance of tomato hybrids for titratable acidity quality traits under poly house conditions ranged from 0.304 to 0.509%.

Table 4.6. Selected Chemical quality parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North *Mecha* District

Locations	Tomato varieties	Juice Content (%)	PH	Total soluble solid (°Brix)	Titretable Acidity (%)
Enguti I	Galilea	87.90a	5.57a	4.94a	1.10a
	Gabbi	77.55b	4.62b	4.07c	0.52c
	Galilea-39	81.44b	4.64b	4.56b	0.91b
	P-Value	**	**	**	**
	LSD (5%)	2.84	0.23	0.09	0.15
	SE ±	0.82	2.66	0.03	0.04
	CV (%)	2.00	2.68	11.25	10.27
Enguti II	Galilea	79.01a	4.93a	4.93b	0.79b
	Gabbi	68.36b	4.33b	5.03b	0.57c
	Galilea-39	74.85 a	4.10b	5.60 a	0.97a
	P-Value	*	*	*	***
	LSD (5%)	4.60	0.37	0.26	0.02
	SE ±	1.33	0.11	0.07	0.05
	CV (%)	3.59	4.81	2.86	13.9
Kollela	Galilea	82.08b	4.77	4.90a	0.98a
	Gabbi	80.25b	4.63	4.08b	0.72c
	Galilea-39	90.16a	4.18	5.00a	0.83b
	P-Value	*	ns	*	**
	LSD (5%)	6.73	0.43	0.35	0.07
	SE ±	1.56	0.12	0.10	0.02
	CV (%)	4.62	5.46	4.40	4.50
Kudmi	Galilea	72.22	5.28a	4.63a	0.48a
	Gabbi	77.77	4.35b	4.63a	0.44b
	Galilea-39	84.29	3.88b	3.82b	0.42c
	P-Value	ns	*	*	**
	LSD (5%)	6.19	0.59	0.41	0.02
	SE ±	1.79	0.17	0.13	0.006
	CV (%)	4.58	7.64	5.39	2.73
Over locations	Galilea	80.30a	5.14a	4.85a	0.84a
	Gabbi	75.98b	4.36b	4.25b	0.56c
	Galilea-39	82.68a	4.32b	4.95a	0.78b
	P-Value	**	**	**	***
	LSD (5%)	2.32	0.33	0.18	0.05
	SE ±	0.70	0.07	0.49	0.01
	CV (%)	3.51	5.89	3.38	6.85

Means within a column sharing common letter(s) are not significantly different, ***=very highly significant, **=highly significant, * significant, LSD=Least Significance Difference, SE=Standard Error, CV=Coefficient of Variation, C. Mean=Combined Mean

4.5. Relationship of Growth and Yield Parameters as Influenced by Hybrid Tomato Varieties Combined over Locations

Pairwise correlation was used to establish relationships between growth and yield parameters of tomatoes (Table 4.7). Results of Pairwise correlation (r) showed that marketable yield per hectare had a strongly significant and positive correlation with plant height ($r=0.44^{**}$), number of primary branches ($r=0.59^{**}$), number of secondary branches ($r=0.41^*$), number of flower clusters per plant ($r=0.83^{**}$), number of flowers per cluster ($r=0.68^{**}$) and number of fruits per cluster ($r=0.74^{**}$), fruit length ($r=0.50^*$) and fruit weight ($r=0.56^*$). Furthermore, total fruit yield had a positive and highly significant association with plant height ($r=0.42^{**}$), number of primary branches ($r=0.55^{**}$), number of secondary branches ($r=0.42^*$), number of flower clusters per plant ($r=0.83^{**}$), number of flowers per cluster ($r=0.67^{**}$) and number of fruits per cluster ($r=0.74^{**}$) and that of marketable yield ($r=0.89^{**}$). On the other hand, marketable and total yield was very highly significant and negatively correlated with fruit diameter ($r=-0.65^{**}$).

The results indicate that varieties with longest height, more number of branches, higher number of flower cluster per plant, number of flowers per cluster and number of fruits per cluster gives higher fruit yield and therefore, plants having higher number of these parameters would be selected for higher yield. Meseret Degefa *et al.* (2012) reported highly significant positive correlation of marketable yield per hectare with most of these parameters. The result is also consistent with the work of Shushay Cherenet *et al.* (2014), who reported that fruit yield increased as the number of branches increased.

Table 4.7. Relationships of growth and yield parameters of hybrid tomato varieties of combined locations under polyhouse structure at Koga Irrigation Scheme in 2022/2023

	PLH	NPBPP	NSBPP	NCPP	NFIPC	NFrPC	FSP	MY	TY	FL	FD	FW
PLH												
NPBPP	0.36ns											
NSBPP	0.29ns	0.49**										
NCPP	0.48**	0.70**	0.66**									
NFIPC	0.40*	0.71*	0.56**	0.77**								
NFrPC	0.38ns	0.66**	0.54**	0.82*	0.84**							
FSP	0.09ns	0.13ns	0.13ns	0.35ns	0.04ns	0.57ns						
MY	0.44**	0.59**	0.41*	0.83**	0.68*	0.74**	0.37ns					
TY	0.42**	0.55**	0.42*	0.83**	0.67**	0.74**	0.39ns	0.89**				
FL	0.03ns	0.41ns	0.31ns	0.28ns	0.25ns	0.29ns	-0.05ns	0.50*	0.18ns			
FD	-0.65ns	-0.13ns	0.01ns	-0.17ns	-0.11ns	0.17ns	-0.14ns	-0.65*	-0.65*	0.63*		
FW	-0.52ns	0.03ns	0.02ns	-0.15ns	-0.11ns	-0.09ns	-0.03ns	0.56*	-0.15ns	0.38*	0.44*	

*PLH=Plant height, NPB=Number of primary branches, NSBPP=Number of Secondary Branches per plant, NCPP=Number of cluster per plant, NFIPC=Number of flowers per cluster, NFrPC=Number of fruits per cluster, FSP=Fruit set percentage, MY=Marketable yield, TY=Total yield, FL=Fruit length, FD=Fruit diameter, FW=Fruit Weight, ns =non-significant, **=highly significant, *=significant*

4.7. Financial Feasibility study of Tomato Production under Polyhouse Structure

Polyhouse production is a capital-intensive technology requiring a substantial investment especially during the initial establishment period. Details of the cost components involved in constructing polyhouses are given in Table 4.8. The construction of 140 m² Polyhouse required a non-land capital investment of 42,750.00 Birr with a total investment cost of 171,000.00 Birr across all locations (140 m² *4). This includes, costs on PVC plastic sheet, wood materials, nail, stretching rope/goma, sand, cement, net and carpenter for construction of polyhouse. The Polyhouse normally lasts for three years of life span for production of tomatoes.

Details of raw material costs for tomato cultivation are shown in Table 4.9. The raw material cost includes the cost of tomato seedlings, chemical costs and fertilizer costs. This was calculated using an estimate of a 25% increase in the second year of production from the first year and a 35% increase in the third year of production from the second year. The other material costs, staking material cost were calculated based on an estimate of a 10% increase in the second year of production from the first and a 15% increase in the third year from the second years of production (Table 4.9).

The average raw material cost for tomato production was 4,706.40 ETB for a single polyhouse structure in the first year of the production season with a total cost of 18,825.61 ETB at all locations. The estimated raw material cost for single polyhouse structure was 5,646.32 ETB and 7,247.83 ETB in the 2nd and 3rd years of production, respectively whereas the estimated total cost of raw material was Birr 22,585.26 and Birr 28,991.31, respectively in the 2nd and 3rd years of production at all locations.

The other costs were summarized under the operational costs, which were calculated in the second and third years of production at 10% and 15% increases, respectively compared to the first and second years respectively. The average operational costs for tomato production during the first years were 27,077.77 ETB for individual polyhouse structures and 114,311.07

ETB for all locations. The estimated operational costs for individual polyhouses in the 2nd and 3rd years of production were 25,512.35 ETB and 24,426.30 ETB, respectively, and the total estimated cost across all locations were 108,649.39 ETB and 105,295.20 ETB, respectively as indicated in Table 4.10.

The total working capital of an investment was calculated by summing up of the initial investment cost and the raw material cost and that of the operational costs which is equal to 54831.45 as indicated in Table 4. 11. In this regard the raw material and operational costs was taken from the first years of production. This could be due to that the second and third years costs are covered from the incomes of the first year of tomato production. Working capital was utilized to calculate the interest and loan repayment of the project, with 70% of the investment being sourced from a loan, while the remaining 30% of the project was covered by the farmers own funds.

Table 4.8. Cost of establishment of an individual polyhouse structure (140m²) and over all locations (140m²*4)

Initial investment cost of individual and total polyhouse structures					
Item	Measurement	Quantity	Unit Price	Total 140 m ²	Total (140 m ² *4)
PVC Plastic sheet	Roll	1	21000	21000	84000
Wood material/bamboo	<u>no</u>	192	50	9600	12000
Nail	Packet	1	3600	3600	14400
Stretching rope	Roll	20	50	1000	4000
Coarse sand	_	1	250	250	1000
Fine sand	_	1	200	200	800
Cement	Quintal	1	1500	1500	6000
Construction of polyhouse	Labor/person	1	3600	3600	14400
Net	<u>no</u>	4	500	2000	8000
Total				42750	171,000

Table 4.9. Variable cost for the production of tomato under polyhouse (140 m²) and over all locations of polyhouse structure (140m²*4)

Raw Material Cost for the individual and total polyhouses														
		1st year				2nd year				3rd year				
Item		Measu rment	Q	UP	Total 140 m ²	Total 140 m ² *4	Q	UP	Total 140 m ²	Total 140 m ² *4	Q	UP	Total 140 m ²	Total 140 m ² *4
Tomato seedlings	Galilea	<u>no</u>	96	5.43	521.28	2085.12	96	6.79	651.84	2607.36	96	9.17	880.32	3521.28
	Galilea39	<u>no</u>	96	6.1	585.6	2342.4	96	7.63	732.48	2929.92	96	10.3	988.8	3955.2
	Gabbi	<u>no</u>	96	6.65	638.4	2553.6	96	8.31	797.76	3191.04	96	11.22	1077.12	4308.48
urea		kg	1.4	41.55	58.17	232.68	1.4	45.705	63.99	255.948	1.4	52.561	73.59	294.3416
NPS		kg	3.4	80.28	273	1091.808	3.4	88.308	300.25	1200.989	3.4	93.53	318	1272.01
Staking material		Roll	10	125	1250	5000	10	137.5	1375	5500	10	158.13	1581.25	6325
Chemical	Redomil	Package	1/4	400	400	1600	1/4	500	500	2000	1/4	675	675	2700
	Altracol	litter	1/4	800	800	3200	1/4	1000	1000	4000	1/4	1350	1350	5400
	Farrate	litter	1/4	180	180	720	1/4	225	225	900	1/4	303.75	303.75	1215
Total cost					4706.45	18825.61			5646.32	22585.26			7247.83	28991.31

Q=Quantity, UP=Unit Price.

Table 4.10. Operational cost for tomato production under each individual polyhouse structure (140 m²) and over all locations of polyhouse structures (140 m²*4)

Operational expenses													
Types of Cost	1st year					2nd year				3rd year			
	Input	Q	UP	Total 140 m ²	Total 140 m ² *4	Q	UP	Total 140 m ²	Total 140 m ² *4	Q	UP	Total 140 m ²	Total 140 m ² *4
Land preparation	Labor	4	200	800	3200	4	220	880	3520	4	253	1012	4048
Weeding cost	Labor	4	125	500	2000	4	137.5	550	2200	4	158.125	632.5	2530
Staking cost	Labor	5	100	500	2000	5	110	550	2200	5	126.5	632.5	2530
Fertilizer application cost	Labor	1	200	200	800	1	220	220	880	1	253	253	1012
Irrigation application cost	Labor	12.5	100	1250	5000	12.5	110	1375	5500	12.5	126.5	1581.25	6325
Pesticide applicator cost	Labor	5	75	375	1500	5	82.5	412.5	1650	5	94.875	474.375	1897.5
Training and Pruning cost	Labor	5	150	750	3000	5	165	825	3300	5	189.75	948.75	3795
Harvesting and Packing cost	Labor	10	150	1500	6000	10	165	1650	6600	10	189.75	1897.5	7590
Transportation and Seller cost	Labor	10	150	1500	6000	10	165	1650	6600	10	189.75	1897.5	7590
Interest and loan repayment				19702.77	78811.07			17399.85	69599.39			15096.93	60387.70
Total cost				27077.77	114311.07			25512.35	108649.39			24426.30	105295.20

Q=Quantity, UP=Unit Price, AVT=Average total cost

Table 4.11. Interest and Loan repayment

Years	Balance	Principal	Interest	Total repayment
0	38382.015	0	0	0
1	25588.01	12794.005	6908.7627	19702.7677
2	12794.005	12794.005	4605.8418	17399.8468
3	0	12794.005	2302.9209	15096.9259
Interest rate at 18%				
Working capital =54831.45				

The marketable tomato yield from the homogeneity analysis in Enguti I, Enguti II, Kollala and Kudmi was 88.35 t/ha, 85.47 t/ha, 87.44 t/ha and 79.28 t/ha, respectively, depending on the location. On the other hand, the marketable yield of tomato for the variety was 83.67 t/ha, 89.11 t/ha and 82.62 t/ha for the Galilea-39, Gabbi and Galilea varieties respectively. The net cash flow was calculated using the average marketable tomato yield for the locations, which corresponds to an average of 85.14 t/ha. The net cash flow was determined for 140 m² of polyhouse area in terms of costs and yields and the average tomato yield was adjusted on a kilogram basis, which corresponds to 1,191.96 kg per 140 m² as indicated in Table 4.12.

The total marketable yield of tomatoes was calculated assuming that the total yield decreases by 10% in the second year of production from the first and decreases by 15% in the third year of production from the second year at each individual location. This could be due to soil fertility status, the occurrence of diseases and the breaking down of the polyhouse structures and the lower sunlight intensity. The average price of tomatoes in Merawi market was 30.33 during the first year of production, which is relatively low compared to the tomato price during the rainy (summer) season because the harvest time of the crop is relatively late due to the late planting of the tomato seedlings. It was estimated that the average price of tomatoes in the second year increased by double from the first year and increased by 15% in the third years of production from the second (Table 4.12). This could be due to the increase in tomato prices and the lack of tomato production in the rainy season.

Table 4.12. Total revenue of tomato under polyhouse structure (140 m²)

Years	Quantity of produce (kg)	Price	Total revenue (Quantity *Price)
0 year	0	0	0
1st year	1191.96	30.33	36152.15
2nd year	1072.76	60.66	65073.62
3rd Year	911.85	70.00	63829.50

An investment or a project to become profitable should have a Net Present Value (NPV) of non negative as indicated by Teferi Deyuu (2016). Accordingly, the Net present value (NPV) of the total returns at 18 % discount rate for three years period of the present study worked out to be 4,135.27 ETB with the benefit cost ratio (BCR) of 1.25 (Table 4.14 and Table 4.15). As the cost-benefit ratio is greater than one and the NPV is positive for these tomato crops, hence production of such crops in the Polyhouse is economically viable. These results coincide with the work of Panwar *et al.*(2013), who reported that the cost benefit ratio of tomato in greenhouse production are greater than one which is economically viable. The result contradicts with the work of Sreenivasa *et al.* (2009), who reported that production of tomatoes in a polyhouse was not found to be economically feasible as the net present value at 10% discount rate was negative, the benefit cost ratio (BCR) was less than one (0.69) and the internal rate of returns to investment was negative (-11.50%), suggesting that the tomato production in polyhouse is not economical.

The payback period for polyhouse production of tomato was found to be 2.1 years of production. An averageGross return (undiscounted) for three years period was 4,367.97 33,914.96 and 3, 2155.37 ETB respectively under polyhouse technologies (Table 4.13). The Internal rate of return (IRR) in polyhouse production of tomato is likely to be 24 per cent at 18% interest rate as shown in Table 4.14. Therefore, production of tomato in a polyhouse structure is highly feasible and profitable.

Table 4.13. Average income statements of a polyhouse structure (140 m²)

Income Statement			
Item	1st year	2nd year	3rd year
Row material cost	4706.40	5646.31	7247.83
Operational cost	27077.77	25512.35	24426.30
Total cost of item	31784.17	31158.66	31674.13
Total revenue	36152.15	65073.62	63829.50
Gross income	4367.97	33914.96	32155.37

Table 4.14. Cash flow statements of a polyhouse structure (140 m²) for tomato production

Cash flow statement				
Item	0 year	1st year	2nd year	3rd year
Investment cost	42750	0	0	0
Row material cost	0	4706.402	5646.31	7247.83
Operational cost	0	27077.77	25512.35	24426.3
Total cost	42750	31784.17	31158.66	31674.13
Revenue	0	36152.15	65073.62	63829.5
Net cash flow	-42750	4367.97	33914.96	32155.37
IRR at 18%	24%			
Payback period	2.1 years			
Net present value at 18% discount rate	4,135.27 Birr			

Table 4.15. Cost benefit ratio analysis of polyhouse structure (140 m²) for tomato production

Cost benefit ratio Analysis					
Year	0 year	1st year	2nd year	3rd year	Total
Initial investment cost	42750	0	0	0	
Row material cost	0	26750.85	26061.07	25948.16	
Operational cost	0	26750.85	26060.77	25948.16	
Total cost	42750	31784.17	31158.66	31674.13	
DF at18%	1	0.89	0.80	0.71	
Discounted Cost	42750	35712.55	38948.33	44611.45	164483.99
Total benefit	0	36152.15	65073.62	63829.50	
DF at 18%	1	0.89	0.80	0.71	
Discounted Benefit	0	39727.63	78401.95	85106	203235.59
BCR ratio at 18% discount rate	1.25				

DF=Discount Factor, BCR=Benefit Cost Ratio, IRR= Internal Rate of Return.

Chapter 5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1. Conclusion

Polyhouse is an important production system of tomato during main rainy season in warm humid areas of Amhara region. Generally, the performance of hybrid varieties in terms of growth and yield under Polyhouse at Koga Irrigation Scheme is different. Except in Kudmi site, Gabbi variety produced the highest marketable yield (90.75 to 103.07 t/ha) and total yield (92.20 to 104.31 t/ha) in all locations as well as combined across the locations (89.11 t/ha) and (90.32 t/ha), respectively. Financial feasibility of the polyhouse showed, net present value of producing tomatoes in the polyhouse with 18% discount rate was non-negative (4,135.27ETB per 140m² area); the benefit to cost ratio was 1.25 and the internal rate of return was 24% at 18% interest rate. The use of Polyhouse for the production of tomatoes during main rainy season is feasible and profitable as it provides protection to tomato crops against extreme weather conditions, create climate manipulation possibilities and improve yield and fruit qualities.

5.2. Recommendation

Polyhouse can be used for the production of tomatoes during the main rainy season in the study area and areas with similar agro-ecology. However, the technology should be constructed in areas with full sunlight without any shade effect. Moreover, the selection of varieties that are suitable for the technology is quit necessary. Accordingly, Gabbi variety of tomatoes can be used for polyhouse production system of tomatoes during the main rainy season as it recorded the highest marketable yield (89.11 t/ha) across the four experimental locations. As the technology is new for tomato production, optimization of agronomic practices including fertilizer, spacing and pest management are also recommended for future researches.

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7. APPENDICES

Appendix Table 1. Mean square of analysis of variance (ANOVA) for growth and phenology parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North Mecha District

Locations	Source of variation	DF	PLH	NPBPP	NSBPP	50%FL	DFH
Enguti I	Variety	2	412.69**	8.15**	2.73ns	30.33**	95.58**
	Replication	3	9.34ns	0.10ns	0.97ns	2.67ns	0.89ns
	Error	6	8.86	0.28	0.76	1.33	1.81
Enguti II	Variety	2	443.08**	9.66**	33.38***	137.33**	123.08*
	Replication	3	4.96ns	0.91ns	2.63ns	2.31ns	8.89ns
	Error	6	15.83	0.40	0.53	4.89	4.31
Kollela	Variety	2	483.68**	4.62*	46.69**	57.58ns	110.25**
	Replication	3	21.32ns	0.09ns	2.04ns	6.78ns	8.75ns
	Error	6	18.07	0.21	1.60	4.03	3.92
Kudmi	Variety	2	435.57*	6.67*	30.51***	68.58**	160.33**
	Replication	3	50.70ns	0.40	0.10ns	9.64ns	2.11
	Error	6	30.03	0.43	0.19	2.47	3.78
Over locations	Variety	2	1255.32***	1.31**	38.57***	125.81**	128.08**
	Location	3	75.85ns	1.45ns	12.46ns	16.95**	37.41**
	Rep (L)	12	50.52ns	0.11ns	2.19ns	2.94ns	7.08ns
	Var*Loc	6	173.23***	5.85***	24.92**	55.67**	122.06**
	Error	33	16.49	0.37	0.88	3.99	3.74

DF=Degree of freedom, *PLH* =Plant Height, *NPBPP*=Number of Primary Branches per plant, *SB*=Number of Secondary Branches per plant, *50%FL*=50%Floweing, *DFH*=Days to First Harvest

Appendix Table 2. Mean square of analysis of variance (ANOVA) for yield related parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North *Mecha* District

Locations	Source of variation	DF	NCPP	NFIPC	NFrPC	FSP
Enguti I	Variety	2	84.67**	2.01**	1.90***	40.42ns
	Replication	3	0.94ns	0.16ns	0.03ns	10.76ns
	Error	6	1.67	0.07	0.02	12.36
Enguti II	Variety	2	63.78**	3.27**	1.25ns	35.32ns
	Replication	3	3.16ns	0.04ns	0.09ns	58.39ns
	Error	6	2.05	0.10	0.13	20.93
Kollela	Variety	2	232.81**	3.80ns	4.77**	117.38ns
	Replication	3	13.09ns	0.17ns	0.06ns	3.10ns
	Error	6	5.42	0.32	0.17	21.69
Kudmi	Variety	2	106.30***	2.65ns	3.72**	193.76**
	Replication	3	5.48ns	0.23ns	0.05ns	9.08ns
	Error	6	1.02	0.21	0.09	6.76
Over locations	Variety	2	81.38**	2.06**	1.25**	28.84ns
	Location	3	67.3ns	1.08*	0.42ns	270.37**
	Rep (L)	12	0.37ns	0.17ns	0.02ns	27.70ns
	Var *Loc	6	135.39**	3.22**	3.46	119.35**
	Error	33	3.87	0.17	0.09	16.10

DF=Degree of Freedom, *NCPP*=Number of Cluster per plant, *NFIPC*=Number of Flower per cluster, *NFrPC*=Number of Fruit per cluster, *FSP*=Fruit set percentage,

Appendix Table 3. Mean square of analysis of variance (ANOVA) for yield parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North Mecha District

Locations	Source of variation	DF	MY(t/ha)	UY (t/ha)	UY (%)	TY(t/ha)
Enguti I	Variety	2	691.83*	8.59***	11.46***	707.85*
	Replication	3	52.39ns	0.31ns	0.40ns	53.84ns
	Error	6	36.43	0.07	0.09	35.61
Enguti II	Variety	2	93.94*	8.74***	8.74***	94.13**
	Replication	3	3.26ns	0.04ns	0.04ns	3.93ns
	Error	6	6.41	0.03	0.03	7.02
Kollela	Variety	2	252.61*	6.75***	8.80**	229.04**
	Replication	3	27.94ns	0.10ns	0.13ns	28.73ns
	Error	6	13.87	0.05	0.05	13.41
Kudmi	Variety	2	510.41**	0.99**	0.99**	499.59**
	Replication	3	34.67ns	0.01ns	0.04ns	34.14ns
	Error	6	17.49	0.02	0.02	17.83
Over locations	Variety	2	193.86**	5.21***	7.14**	157.41**
	Location	3	200.28ns	3.75**	4.03**	241.83ns
	Rep (L)	12	32.31ns	0.01ns	0.03ns	32.09ns
	Var*Loc	6	451.65**	6.45**	87.16**	457.73**
	Error	33	21.30	0.07	0.08	21.48

DF=Degree of Freedom, MY=Marketable yield, UY=Unmarketable Yield and TY=Total Yield.

Appendix Table 4. Mean square of analysis of variance (ANOVA) for physical quality parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North *Mecha* District

Locations	Source of variation	DF	FL	FD	FW
Enguti I	Variety	2	1.06*	1.25ns	258.92**
	Replication	3	0.09ns	0.64ns	35.06ns
	Error	6	0.05	0.23	8.69
Enguti II	Variety	2	0.81**	0.79**	286.43*
	Replication	3	0.02ns	0.95ns	33.47ns
	Error	6	0.03	0.03	13.90
Kollela	Variety	2	2.21ns	0.79*	467.92*
	Replication	3	0.13ns	0.01	27.80ns
	Error	6	0.31	0.04	28.10
Kudmi	Variety	2	1.08*	1.85ns	157.36ns
	Replication	3	0.001ns	0.07ns	30.07ns
	Error	6	0.04	0.29	22.45
Over locations	Variety	2	3.97**	3.81**	886.1**
	Location	3	0.4ns	0.49ns	93.48ns
	Rep (L)	12	0.06ns	0.23ns	17.25ns
	Var*Loc	6	0.4**	0.35ns	101.51*
	Error	33	0.84	0.15	23.22

DF=Degree of Freedom, *FL*=Fruit Length, *FD*=Fruit Diameter, *FW*=Fruit Weight

Appendix Table 5. Mean square of analysis of variance (ANOVA) for chemical quality parameters of hybrid tomato varieties under polyhouse structure at different *Kebeles* in North *Mecha* District

Locations	Source of variation	DF	PH	TSS	TA	JC
Enguti I	Variety	2	1.18***	0.75***	0.35**	109.26**
	Replication	3	0.03	0.008ns	0.009ns	16.25ns
	Error	6	0.02	0.003	0.007	2.7
Enguti II	Variety	2	0.74*	0.53*	0.16***	115.28**
	Replication	3	0.01ns	0.08	0.0002ns	11.86ns
	Error	6	0.05	0.02	0.0001	7.08
Kollela	Variety	2	0.39ns	1.03*	0.07**	111.25ns
	Replication	3	0.08ns	0.03ns	0.003ns	2.33ns
	Error	6	0.06	0.04	0.002	15.11
Kudmi	Variety	2	2.03*	0.87*	0.0042**	146.17**
	Replication	3	0.24ns	0.04	0.0002ns	4.63ns
	Error	6	0.12	0.06	0.0002	12.80
Over locations	Variety	2	3.40**	2.29**	0.34***	184.70**
	Location	3	0.61**	1.53ns	0.43**	243.66**
	Rep (L)	12	0.03ns	0.12ns	0.003ns	24.37ns
	Var*Loc	6	0.31*	0.30**	0.08**	99.09**
	Error	33	0.07	0.03	0.002	7.83

DF=Degree of Freedom, *JC*=Juice Content, *PH*=Percentage Hydrogen, *TA*=Titrable Acidity and *TSS*=Total Soluble Solid

Appendix Figure 1. Constructions of polyhouse structure

Appendix Figure 2. Planting of tomato seedlings under polyhouse

Appendix Figure 3. Filed activities and visiting tomatoes in the polyhouse

Appendix Figure 4. Staking of tomato plants inside the polyhouse

Appendix Figure 5. Vegetative and fruit performance of tomato inside the polyhouse

Appendix Figure 6. Tomato data collection and measurement inside the polyhouse

Appendix Figure 7. Harvesting, weighing, soaring and packing of tomatoes

Appendix Figure 8. Laboratory work for quality parameters of tomato

Appendix Figure 9. Farmers field day on tomato production in the polyhouse

BIOGRAPHY

The author, Zenebe Abebu was born in 09 January 1995 G.C in North *Shewa Zone* at *Ankober Woreda* in Amhara Region, Ethiopia. He attended his elementary School at *Wodera Mariam* Primary School from 2004 to 2011G.C. He completed his Secondary and Preparatory School education at *Ankober* General Secondary and Preparatory School from 2012 to 2016 G.C. He joined Samara University in 2017 G.C, College of Dry Land Agriculture and completed his study with Bachelor of Science degree in Horticulture Science on 14 July 2019 G.C. After his successful graduation, he was employed in Samara University on 10 October 2019 G.C and served as a graduate assistance for two years. In 2022 G.C, he joined Bahir Dar University, College of Agriculture and Environmental Science, School of Post graduate programs to pursue his M.Sc. degree in Horticulture.